

Mary Anning statue unveiled p. 28

GeoHistories

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Editorial

What a vibrant society the History of Geology Group is. This edition of *GeoHistories* reflects the activities of its members over one six-month period. During this time there were three thought-provoking and well-attended online talks and two absolutely brilliant weekend field trips. In addition, our members have both written and reviewed books and papers and attended history-of-geology-related events – all of which we are pleased to record in this members' magazine.

Being predominantly a record of the transactions of the group, *GeoHistories* does not run to totally themed issues. Nevertheless, it is astonishing quite how many micro-themes seem to crop up. It may be unsurprising that Nina Morgan's visit to Malvern for HOGG's May field trip should have inspired her to give us a 'Tailings...' article about water divining, but it is perhaps more of a coincidence that Anne Barrett should have spoken to us about A.C. Ramsay within months of a visit to Anglesey during which his fieldwork was discussed *in situ* and his final resting place was visited by eager HoGs.

Another theme that emerged as copy flowed into my inbox was the place and importance of fine art in the history of geology. Two fascinating book reviews by Douglas Palmer and Sue Newell clearly complement Keith Nicholls and Cynthia Burek's article on the work of surveyor and landscape painter, Thomas Compton. Then Nina Morgan's piece on the geological decoration that is so integral to Oxford's Natural History Museum shows that the aesthetic element of the subject is clearly not confined to two dimensions.

The celebration of the contribution of women to the history of geology has long concerned Cynthia Burek, the subject of this edition's 'HoG's Life', and Phil James' first-hand account of the unveiling of the new Anning statue shows that at least one woman is now recognised by a wider public.

Historians of science are well used to appreciating the importance of contingency, and in this issue Nigel Woodcock reminds us of the importance of Sedgwick's early life in Dent, while Gordon Chancellor reflects on the influence that a gift of Lyell's *Principles* would have over the young Charles Darwin.

But perhaps the most marked coincidence in this edition of *GeoHistories* is the inclusion of two boyhood tales telling how the serendipitous finding of a fossil led to two lifetimes of palaeontological discovery: Phil James as a dedicated 'amateur' – in the very best sense of the word – and Dave Williams in a long and distinguished professional career.

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As you read this issue of *GeoHistories* the first 100 Geological Heritage Sites (GHS) will have been designated by the International Union of Geosciences (IUGS). A further 50 sites will be announced in 2023. Each site has been selected by a voting process as ‘a place with geological elements and/or processes of scientific international relevance, used as a reference, and/or with a substantial contribution to the development of geological sciences through history.’ There are eleven history-of-geology sites in the first batch, and one more to be announced in the second. It will be interesting to see those awarded the status and to read the citations. As I understand, Siccar Point will be one of the designated sites. I have some reservations about sites chosen for such prominence; it is inevitably a subjective business. As always in the history of geology, it is difficult to select one place or event without considering it in a wider context. Siccar Point can only be fully understood in the context of Hutton’s earlier serendipitous ‘discovery’ of unconformable strata in Jedburgh, and the subsequent confirmation that what he had observed there extended

across country to be found in a tributary of the Teviot. Thus, Siccar Point was the third location in Hutton’s chain of confirmation, so arguably it was his sharing of the Siccar Point angular junction with fellow philosophers that gave it meaning and lent real significance to the site. In this, perhaps Siccar Point deserves its status in the history of geology and the right to be shared as a GHS. I wonder how the designation will affect access to the site?

Another internationally important site of Hutton’s, his ‘Section’ at Salisbury Crags in Edinburgh, has, for some – not perhaps entirely justified – ‘safety reasons’, been fenced off since 2019. HOGG was signatory to a letter, coordinated by Edinburgh Geological Society, asking Historic Environment Scotland (mission: ‘to share and celebrate our heritage with the world’) to restore access to this important site. So far, no action has been forthcoming. Maybe the international GHS status of Siccar Point will generate enthusiasm for all things Hutton? If so, perhaps the IUGS could fire some of that enthusiasm towards gaining reasonable access to Hutton’s Section? If IUGS transferred GHS status to Salisbury Crags might it possibly open up the way to access? Hutton’s Section is, after all, substantially significant in the context.

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Members’ News & Correspondence

Letter

Sir,
The Mary Anning statue in Lyme Regis

While walking the Jurassic Coast Path last month (September 2022), I broke for a rest day in Lyme Regis with the express purpose of admiring the seafront statue of Mary Anning, unveiled to the public in May this year.

That seemingly simple task presented two problems which, I would like to think, might be remedied as soon as possible. Firstly: Where was it? I sought directions from numerous people. Unsurprisingly, visitors to Lyme did not know what I was talking about, and a local resident, although aware of a recent statue to a local celebrity, could not tell me its exact whereabouts. Eventually I was told that if I faced the sea at Bridge Street, turned left – in the opposite direction to the Cobb – and kept walking beside the sea to the far end, I would find Mary facing east, striding forth purposefully towards the fossiliferous foreshore below Black Ven. For technophiles, its ‘what3words’ location is birds.feared.burden. But some simple signage would really help.

The second problem concerns a missing plaque. In front of the sculptor Denise Dutton’s striking statue of Mary is carved her name and dates (1799-1847) – nothing else! I spent

some time explaining to those taking photographs of her exactly who she was and why she deserved such a splendid memorial. There is just enough room beneath the statue for a small plaque with a brief synopsis of her life, and her significance.

Street signage and a biographical plaque beneath the statue would, in my view, greatly enhance the ‘Visitor Experience’, and encourage people to develop their new-found interest in the History of Geology.

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R.I.P.

Since the last issue of *GeoHistories* we have learned of the death of **Dr Peter Aubrey Sabine (1924-2022)**. Peter enjoyed a long and successful career at the British Geological Survey and Museum of Practical Geology, retiring in 1984 as Deputy Director and Chief Scientific Officer. Peter remained active until the end of his life. Having in retirement developed an interest in the history of geology (among many other interests), Peter was an enthusiastic member of HOGG and other societies and gave many talks – most recently on Charles Darwin’s geological work.

Lyell, Darwin and the principle of reasoning in geology

Online talk, March 2022

Gordon Chancellor

As many HOGG members will know, Charles Lyell (1797-1875) published his expensive three-volume *Principles of Geology* over the period from 1830 to 1833. In the first volume

Charles Lyell © NPG, London

he reviewed the history of geology (rather selectively) then set about establishing the correct ‘principles’ for understanding the causes that led to the present configuration of the Earth’s surface. Lyell argued that geologists should only consider as true those causes which could be seen by reliable witnesses operating at the surface of the Earth today, such as the volcanic eruptions that have built Etna or the erosion of its cliffs by the sea. This actualistic method was nothing new, but Lyell went further by limiting admissible causes to those which acted gradually and with uniform intensity.

When Lyell’s first volume appeared, it was immediately recognized as a major contribution to establishing geology as a true science. Lyell’s insistence that only gradual and uniformly-acting causes were admissible was, however, almost universally rejected by his geological colleagues. Lyell claimed that the rock record only *appeared* to show a gradual cooling of the Earth, and that the fossil record only *appeared* to show a gradual progression from simple to more complex forms. These were illusions, Lyell said, caused by geologists’ failure to understand both the unimaginably great age of the Earth and the extreme imperfection of the geological record. He made fun of those who appealed to catastrophic events to explain anything which did not appear to have a present-day analogue, such as those French geologists who believed that the great mountain belts of the World had been uplifted in gigantic paroxysms. He got over the obvious objection of the ‘cooling Earth’ palaeontologists, by arguing that the evidence for a warmer climate, such as the tropical tree fern fossils found in the Coal Measures (which he did not dispute), merely proved a warmer climate for the European Carboniferous. Lyell’s theory was that the warmth was due to higher sea levels (therefore subsided crust) over what is now Europe and that this would have been balanced by lower sea levels (therefore elevated crust) somewhere else in the World.

Charles Darwin Public Domain

When Charles Darwin (1809-1881) graduated from Cambridge in 1831 he was regarded by his mentor J. S. Henslow as an exceptionally gifted young naturalist. Darwin had been put off studying geology by the ‘Wernerian’ lecturers he had been exposed to earlier in Edinburgh, where, unlike Cambridge, dangerous Continental ideas were openly discussed. These ideas included a belief that granite was formed early in the Earth’s history or – far worse – that life on Earth had ‘developed’ by gradual transmutation of species. Perhaps to rectify Darwin’s sympathy for such radical ideas, Henslow lent him the Prussian Alexander von Humboldt’s *Personal Narrative* of his South American travels. Humboldt had studied geology in the 1790s but, having been thwarted in his plan to study the geology of Europe by Napoleon’s rampages, had become the first geologist to report back on the rocks of the New World. Henslow also asked Adam Sedgwick to take Darwin with him on his summer fieldwork among the ‘Transition’ rocks of North Wales.

John Stevens Henslow Public Domain

Darwin was enchanted by Humboldt and determined to travel himself, falling hook, line and sinker for geology. As a man rich enough never to have to work for a living, on returning home from the fieldtrip Darwin found the offer to travel around the world as naturalist on H.M.S. *Beagle*. His father would foot the bill, once his brother-in-law – Darwin’s uncle (and future father-in-law), Josiah Wedgwood – had convinced him that such a dangerous undertaking would be well worth the effort.

The *Beagle*’s Captain, Robert FitzRoy, gave Darwin a copy of Lyell’s first volume. Its frontispiece shows the so-called ‘Temple of Serapis’ near Naples, chosen by Lyell to show how in just sixteen centuries the Roman columns had been buried in Vesuvian ash and plunged at least 7m beneath the sea by an earthquake, then elevated still standing, back to almost their original altitude.

The famous frontispiece to Lyell’s *Principles of Geology* showing the columns of the ‘Temple of Serapis’ Public Domain

Lyell, Darwin & the principle of reasoning

At Darwin's very first landfall, at the Cape Verdes only days after leaving England, he immediately saw a marine limestone containing recent fossils elevated high above beach level. What more dramatic confirmation of Lyell's belief in the power of elevation and subsidence could anyone have hoped for?

Lyell's first volume had dealt comprehensively with the 'inorganic' causes operating on the Earth's surface. When he came to write his second volume he found he needed greatly to expand his treatment of 'organic' geological causes, so much so that Volume 2 (1832) was entirely devoted to these causes and his planned reconstruction of Tertiary Earth history became a separate Vol. 3 (1833). This allowed Lyell to concentrate in Vol. 2 on refuting the 'evolution' theory of Jean-Baptiste Lamarck, published in his *Philosophie Zoologique* of 1809. Lyell was planning a new way of dating rocks using suites of fossils rather than 'index' species. He had made large collections of molluscs from across the Continent and had had them identified by the best palaeontologists. He worked out a statistical process for calculating how the percentage of recent species present in any particular suite provided a means of estimating its age and in Vol. 3 he used this to revise the division of the Tertiary period. In order for this estimate to mean anything it was obvious that species must be assumed to have come and gone at a uniform rate, giving him a good reason for refuting Lamarck who had argued that species generally only change when their 'circumstances' change. By 1830 Lamarck was dead and his supporters, for example Étienne Geoffroy Saint-Hilaire, were facing an increasingly hostile intellectual climate dominated by George Cuvier, who had more or less invented the idea of extinction of species caused by changing environments. Geoffroy had collected thousands of mummified ibises from Ancient Egypt which Cuvier showed were identical to the living species, thus (he said) disproving 'evolution'. Lamarck on the other hand had explained this lack of change by saying the birds' environment had not changed!

Another reason why Lyell had to deny 'evolution' was his certainty that unless he did so he would outrage the Anglican establishment, thus preventing a fair hearing for his less sensitive new ideas. We know, however, from Lyell's private notebooks that the main reason he had to refute Lamarck was that he loathed the idea that 'Man' might have had an ancestor among the apes. All this resulted in Lyell's Vol. 2 being the best summary of the evidence for and against evolution that

Jean-Baptiste Lamarck

Public Domain

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Gordon Chancellor

Darwin could have had with him as he discovered all sorts of evidence which challenged Lyell's account.

Darwin received his copy of Vol. 2 in Montevideo in November 1832, just after discovering a low cliff on the Patagonian coast which contained a rich harvest of fossil mammal bones and teeth. This site, called Bahia Blanca, was so important in undermining Darwin's belief in the fixity of species that he alluded to it in the very first sentence of *The Origin of Species* in 1859. He knew enough to recognize that the animals he found there were almost certainly extinct species, yet some of them – the bony-plated *Glyptodon* for example – seemed similar to animals living today, like the armadillo. Lyell had said that species were created where the environment would suit them but, if this were the case, why Darwin wondered were these creatures extinct if the deposits in which they were entombed were so obviously like the deposits forming on the coast today? He thought about this throughout his three years in South America, concluding in 1835 that perhaps species were not always perfectly adapted to their environments and that perhaps they had fixed life spans. Even though he was totally converted to Lyell's methodology and his belief in the Earth's crust's continual vertical oscillations, Darwin's conclusions regarding species forced him to break away from the master on this and several other issues covered in Vol. 2 of the *Principles*. Within a year of the end of the voyage Darwin regarded the similarities between, for example, the *Glyptodon* and the armadillo as indications of their common descent. At that time, it was too early to reveal his conclusions so in one of his first papers he referred to such species as 'representative'.

I don't have space in this short essay to consider the many other discoveries Darwin made on the voyage which convinced him by the time he returned to England in late 1836 that species were unstable. Everyone knows that the Galápagos were crucial, mainly for triggering Darwin's realization that species were descended from similar species, often when their environments changed or when they became isolated, as for example when they become stranded on an oceanic island. It was not for another two years, however, that he discovered how this happened by the process he called natural selection. It was another two decades before Lyell convinced Darwin that he must publish his research in the book we now call *The Origin*.

In addition to the large number of biological and palaeontological specimens Darwin sent home and farmed out to specialists for publication, he reserved his many important geological discoveries for publication by himself,

Glyptodon (top) and modern armadillo

Hunadam CC BY-SA 4.0

Lyell, Darwin & the principle of reasoning

writing three books: *Coral Reefs* of 1842, *Volcanic Islands* of 1844 and *Geological Observations on South America* of 1846. He also wrote some long and significant papers.

Darwin's geological map of Patagonia
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Darwin's geological publications well repay careful study today, not least because they show his profound understanding of how global tectonics are continuously influencing the distribution of life, as for example in his explanation for how coral atolls are formed by oceanic subsidence. Lyell was an instant convert to Darwin's explanation and *Coral Reefs* is a masterclass in showing how by applying geological time to a range of clearly related natural phenomena they can sometimes be revealed to be an historical sequence. In the case of coral reefs, the tiniest creatures, given enough time, work with crustal mobility literally to shape the face of the Earth. Darwin later used the same basic methodology to show how all life has evolved over time from a common ancestor, although palaeontologists know that with fossils it is far trickier to discriminate the true signs of descent (homologies) from those that convergence has made *appear* similar (analogies).

Having experienced a huge earthquake in Chile and seen the coast elevated overnight, with enormous volcanoes erupting around him, Darwin found the fossil forest at Agua de la Zorra which we now know to have been buried by

Gordon Chancellor

volcanic ash (see Patrick Boylan's article in *GeoHistories* April 2021, p.23). In a footnote in *Coral Reefs* Darwin explained – wrongly as we now know – that the trees had been submerged under the sea then re-elevated by thousands of feet, like a gigantic Temple of Serapis, and he praised Lyell for providing him with the 'eyes' to see how this could have happened. Both Lyell and Darwin were obsessed with vertical crustal mobility and they were both rather slow to understand the implications of Louis Agassiz's belief in a global Ice Age. The only publication Darwin ever regretted was his paper on the 'Parallel Roads of Glen Roy' of 1839 in which he argued strenuously that the 'roads' were sea beaches, the relics of a much higher sea level around the coast of Britain, the same way as the 'roads' he had studied at Coquimbo in Chile were caused by the elevation of the Andes.

Darwin's Observations on the Parallel Roads of Glen Roy
Archive.org/Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society of London

A few years after his paper it became obvious to most geologists that the 'roads' at Glen Roy were relics of an ice dammed lake, but Darwin was very reluctant to give up his marine explanation. Martin Rudwick has shown, however, that Darwin applied his belief in crustal mobility using impeccable methodology so that his paper was not the 'great failure' that he thought it was. Indeed, it was Darwin's 'tenacity' when it came to applying his theories that allowed him twenty years later to convince the majority of scientists that evolution was a fact.

There is far more that could be said about Darwin's geological theories and I hope to do this in a future HOGG talk, for example his own version of 'craters of elevation', a theory Lyell had rejected. I would also mention tantalizing statements in Darwin's books that he thought there might be a chain of volcanoes under the mid-Atlantic and that he saw evidence that South America and Africa were once part of the same continent.

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The life and geological work of Sir Andrew Crombie Ramsay (1814-1891)

It was Ramsay's mapping of the Island of Arran that first brought him to the attention of Henry De la Beche and the Geological Survey. In 1840 Ramsay exhibited a map and model of the island at the British Association for the Advancement of Science (BAAS). The following year he published *The Geology of the Island of Arran from Original Survey*.

Ramsay's *The Geology of the Island of Arran from Original Survey*

Ramsay was quickly invited to join the Geological Survey with which he was to enjoy a long association, rising from Assistant Geologist in 1841, through the post of Local Director for England and Wales, to become Director General from 1867 until his retirement in 1881. He was involved in the surveying for no fewer than 45 of the Survey's one-inch maps: twenty-nine of Wales, one of Scotland, and the others of the Midlands and Central England. For much of this time, he also held lecturing posts, first at University College London, and later at the Royal School of Mines.

Ramsay's work on denudation was presented in *The Causes and Amount of Geological Denudations* at a Royal Institution (R.I.) Friday Evening Discourse in March 1847. Continuing to work in Wales, he made a particular study of glacial geology, forming theories that caused considerable controversy. However, undeterred by the sceptical reception of his ideas, he presented his evidence at another R.I. Discourse in March 1850: *The Geological Phenomena that have produced or modified the Scenery of North Wales*. He continued his glacial studies in Britain, Europe and North America, as well as visiting Greenland and New Zealand. He studied the geology of Gibraltar and noted that of the opposite coast of Africa. He also wrote on the River Po in Italy (1872), on the History of the Mediterranean (1878), and managed to set out his ideas concerning geological time.

It was a great testament to his abilities when Ramsay was elected FRS in 1849, just 9 years after his geological debut. In

1862 he became President of the Geological Society and in 1875 he gave evidence to the Royal Commission on the Geological Survey. He regularly attended the BAAS over a period of 40 years, chairing section C Geology three times and being the Association's President in 1880. He was knighted in 1881.

From the time that Ramsay joined the Geological Survey in 1841, he and De la Beche were geologically 'consolidated' until the latter's death in 1855. It is impossible to separate their work at the 'Survey' from that at the other organisations that Henry De la Beche, geologist, entrepreneur / opportunist, and mentor also founded:

- The Mining Record Office
- The Museum of Economic, later Practical Geology
- The Government School of Mines and of Science Applied to the Arts, renamed from 1861 to that which we know it by: The Royal School of Mines (RSM)

Ramsay continued his Survey work in Pembrokeshire even after his 1848 appointment as professor at University College London and his later appointment to the Professorship of Geology at the RSM in 1851. There, De la Beche and Ramsay worked together on both RSM matters and the Geological Survey.

I have been working on the RSM collections and those of Ramsay as part of my PhD thesis. In this work I have come to understand how a group of colleagues, intent on their science and the promulgation of it, interact and make new discoveries, working on evidence and facts in their research and teaching. This appears to be very much part of the zeitgeist of the 19th century, which involved a strong desire for education amongst much of the general population. So, De la Beche's educationally-based organisations must be seen within the context of both a government-lead drive for science teaching and the mid-19th century spirit of the age – a spirit of self-help and social mobility through education. Andrew Crombie Ramsay took a large part in that enterprise, and his story is illustrated by his papers held in Imperial College Archives.

Sir Andrew Crombie Ramsay in old age. Portrait by his daughter Miss Violet Ramsay

The Ramsay papers consist of letters, drawings, notebooks and diaries. As well as corresponding copiously with colleagues on the Geological Survey, Ramsay enjoyed a wide connection with the wider scientific community, nationally and internationally. The entries in his notebooks and diaries vary in length and detail, but from them we learn that he was an avid reader, both of geological and more general literature. He reflected on his social life and his relationships with women including, eventually, his marriage to Louisa Williams. He noted with whom and where he dined, and where he went on holiday. He also wrote about his colleagues, and his professional travels abroad as well as about his geological observations, his lectures and the development of the Geological Survey, the Mining Record Office, the Museum of Economic/Practical Geology and the RSM. His health was also mentioned, from injuring a knee in the field, through an account of the overwork that caused him to relinquish his of lecturing duties in 1860, to his loss of an eye due to severe infection in 1878.

Both as a child, and in his marriage, he clearly enjoyed a happy family life, and the diaries show him as a loving, generous and fair man, with a great sense of humour. Not wishing to follow the family tradition of working in business, he struck out on his own, forging a highly successful life in geology and teaching. Ramsay was a self-made geologist. He displayed intelligence, integrity and tenacity in his studies and in his dealings with individuals and commanded much professional and personal respect. His sensitive and caring nature was combined with a great sense of fun, making him a central figure amongst the fraternity of Survey geologists and colleagues at the RSM. His papers reveal all these traits and more besides – including his expertise in drawing, the writing of doggerel and, of course, in serious teaching and research.

Ramsay's geological career began with his mapping of the Isle of Arran and although he knew the chemist Lyon Playfair (1818-1898), and the geologist Charles Lyell (1797-1875), it was his introduction to the

wider geological fraternity at that BAAS meeting in Glasgow in 1840 that really launched his career, thanks to two early mentors. J. P. Nichol (1804-1859), Professor of Astronomy at Glasgow University, made Ramsay secretary of the Association's Arran model subcommittee, which introduced him to many of the established geologists.

It was one of these, Roderick Impey Murchison (1792-1871), who, recognising Ramsay's talents, later introduced him to De la Beche. Also, during that 1840 meeting, at a Red Lions' dinner, Ramsay first met Edward Forbes (1815-1854) and Edwin Lankester

Edward Forbes

(1814-1874). As he noted in his diary: '... I then discovered that the most promising young scientific men of the day were as remarkable for their mirth and humour as for their scientific acquirements...'

Ramsay really hit it off with the founder of the Red Lions, the ever likable and gregarious naturalist Edward Forbes. The Red Lion Club, which had its origins at the 1839 BAAS meeting in Birmingham, was just one of the fraternities that Forbes created. It was a club for the Association's younger, less well-off 'philosophers', who dined together in pubs rather than the more formal, expensive venues chosen by their more established colleagues. It enabled these younger men to share their knowledge as they enjoyed a very jolly camaraderie.

Doggerel composed by Edward Forbes for a meeting of the Red Lions

Ramsay and Edward Forbes had a great deal in common. They had each spent many childhood hours wandering about the countryside: Ramsay in Scotland and Arran, Forbes on the Isle of Man. Both had taken a close interest in nature and had been keen to apply their nascent scientific understanding to their observations; experiences they would put to good use later in life. Neither attained a degree; although Forbes began to study medicine at university, he threw it up to pursue his passion for natural history. These similar early-life experiences, coupled with their natural capacities for comradeship, led to a particular affinity and trust between the pair. They wrote to each other openly and honestly, often discussing their colleagues, including De la Beche. They found their Director variously pleasant and accommodating or curmudgeonly, but despite his uncertain temperament, he always seemed to command their respect. De la Beche's powers of persuasion with government officials were legendary and Ramsay and Forbes knew that their interesting and secure careers were only possible because they worked in institutions that he had been able to establish.

Ramsay and Forbes, who both had posts at the RSM and on the Survey, discussed managing their colleagues in the field and in the Museum of Practical Geology. Of course, they also communicated about geological matters, working out their theories, both in letters and face-to-face. Forbes' death

Sir Andrew Crombie Ramsay

in 1854 from a renal disorder was a blow to Ramsay, whose diary records his regret at not being present. It was also a huge loss to Ramsay's colleagues and even, according to Charles Darwin, to 'natural sciences' more generally.

Despite the camaraderie and jollity, the work was hard. They were outdoors in all conditions and weathers, dressed in clothing that would be considered inherently unsuitable by today's standards. Their basic tools, though, were perhaps less problematic as, in essence, they were so similar to today's. But transport, both for the survey staff and their specimens and papers was very tough. In fact, in many areas it was virtually nonexistent, necessitating the hire of ponies. Once, in 1845, Ramsay even had to buy a pony as the 10-mile hike to his surveying area, followed by the onerous survey itself,

Sections drawn by A.C. Ramsay

and then the 10-mile walk back to his residence was 'too great for his legs to stand it.' Nevertheless, sometimes shank's pony was the only way. There was certainly much tramping for the Royal Hammerers!

Accommodation was also clearly of variable quality: sometimes in good inns, sometimes in inns of poorer quality, and sometimes in a private house or guest house. Having spent his first years with the survey in Wales, mapping and studying the geology, Ramsay made many connections with

A road map centring on Dolaucothi drawn by Edward Forbes

Anne Barrett

people there. One place he always found a welcome was in Dolaucothi in Wales, where he had made the acquaintance of Mr Johnes and his family. A friendship developed that lasted their lifetimes. In 1850, Ramsay met his wife when staying in the Rectory at Llanfairynghornwy on Anglesey. They were engaged in 1851, and married in 1852.

Ramsay's life of lecturing, writing and official work, as well as much time in the field, began to take their toll. In 1860, while surveying in Scotland, he complained of weariness. To enable him to take things easier, he relinquished his lecturing to Joseph Beete Jukes (1811-1869), a Geological Survey colleague. Eventually Ramsay and the family went abroad. Officially this was for 6 months but if anyone asked, he instructed, 'several months is a convenient word'. It was to be said that he was not seriously ill and was actually 'so much better already, that he could do a hard day's work in the office, even though tired in the evening.'

Ramsay and Louisa celebrated their silver wedding anniversary in 1877, as he noted in his diary, where he also recollected their wedding day. Still working in the field on a BAAS meeting trip in Scotland in 1878, Ramsay again complained of fatigue. He was also finding it difficult to keep up with modern developments such as the use of the microscope to compare sample rock sections, declaring: 'I cannot see what use slides can be to a field man, I don't believe in looking at a mountain with a microscope.' According to Geikie, Ramsay had become an old man at 63 – prematurely aged by a life of physical and mental toil and official worry.

His contributions to geology were acknowledged by two events in 1880: on 1st December he was awarded a Royal Society Royal medal, 'for his long continued and successful labours in geology and physical geography'. The University of Glasgow also awarded him an L.L.D. degree.

1881 was an eventful final professional year for Ramsay: he was knighted for his services, the second edition of his North Wales memoir for the Survey was published, and then, as President of the Geological Section of the BAAS for the last time, he gave a paper to Section C on the *On the Origin, Progress and Present State of British Geology, especially since the first meeting of the British Association at York in 1831*. He retired from the survey on 31st December, thus concluding a long and fruitful academic career, fulfilling his early promise and solidly rebutting his family's qualms about his unorthodox choice of career. Sometimes the life must have seemed a bit like a circus, travelling from place to place and addressing so many different audiences. But Ramsay left active service in good heart and for ten years, until his death in 1891, he enjoyed a quiet and happy retirement in his beloved Beaumaris. He truly was Royal Hammerer extraordinaire.

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Adam Sedgwick's early life

The Dent Fault of northwest England is one of the earliest regionally important faults to be recorded in the UK as well as one of those that has helped us understand better how faults in general work.

The Dent Fault separates the strongly deformed Lower Palaeozoic rocks of the Lake District from the nearly flat-lying Carboniferous rocks of the Yorkshire Dales to the east. In March 1785, Adam Sedgwick was born in the village of Dent, just on the Dales side of the fault (Clark and Hughes 1890; Speakman 1982). His father was the local vicar and, after 1794, also the schoolmaster at Dent Grammar School. Adam later remembered how his rambles over the local fells made him familiar with the fossils of the Carboniferous Limestone. In those rambles and certainly when he transferred to the larger Sedbergh School in 1799 aged 16, Adam must have noticed the abrupt disappearance of the Carboniferous limestones several kilometres along his north-westward walk to school.

Of course, Sedgwick was taught no geology at Sedbergh, but rather the mathematics and classics required to gain a scholarship at the University of Cambridge. Sedgwick went up to Trinity College in 1804. He worked hard, first to graduate and then, in 1810 to earn his Fellowship at Trinity. But this all came at some considerable cost to his health. His well-being was not improved by the long hours of teaching required of a Fellow. Sedgwick was however recharged by his vacation visits back to Dent, with

Adam Sedgwick. Public Domain

all the outdoor pursuits that these offered. When Cambridge's Woodwardian Professorship of Geology became vacant in 1818, Sedgwick applied and won the vote, despite his lack of formal geological training. Famously, he is said to have remarked that 'Hitherto I have never turned a stone; henceforth I will leave no stone unturned'. At last, he had licence for the field work that suited his temperament.

Sedgwick's research on the Dent Fault

For the next four years, Sedgwick taught himself geology in a series of arduous walking tours in areas from Devon and Dorset to Derbyshire and Durham. In 1822 he was drawn back to the Lakes and Dales, returning in the following two years to build up a large volume of field observations.

However, Sedgwick's preference for outdoor over indoor work meant that this important research was not to be presented to the Geological Society for seven years (Sedgwick 1831) and not to be published in full for a further five years (Sedgwick 1836a)

Cross sections across the Dent Fault Zone in Barbondale, south of Dent. Upper section from Sedgwick (1836); lower section modified from Thomas & Woodcock (2015)

Sedgwick's published cross sections show the geometrical evidence for a continuous NNE-striking fault zone over a 30-kilometre-long segment centred on Sedbergh. Sedgwick correctly identified an unconformity between Lower Carboniferous red beds ('Old Red Sandstone') and underlying Lower Palaeozoic rocks ('Greywacke'), and a 500-metre-wide zone of steeply dipping or folded Carboniferous rocks. However, compared with modern sections, he wrongly placed the main fault at the eastern edge of this steep zone, rather than further west. More recent sections have the eastern feature essentially as a synclinal fold hinge line, weakly faulted in places.

Sedgwick's views on the mechanics of the Dent and related faults also differ from more recent thinking. He envisaged that "...we find ourselves on the very line of ancient convulsion, by which the whole craggy ridge has been torn off from the escarpment, and tumbled over into the valley in which it now stands on edge..." and that "Many of the great movements above described, appear to have been produced by an action both violent and of short duration" (Sedgwick 1836b, pp. 62–64). Sedgwick's catastrophist view of faulting owed much to the contemporary writings of Élie de Beaumont (e.g. 1831). Of course, we now know that the slip in a single faulting event is typically less than a metre, so that the total displacement of at least 0.5 kilometres on the Dent Fault was accumulated over hundreds of individual events of modest magnitude.

This modern revision of thinking on the Dent Fault should not take away from the observational and

interpretational skill that Adam Sedgwick showed in delineating and diagnosing the Dent Fault and the complimentary Pennine Fault to its northwest.

Cropped structural map of northern England by John Phillips (1836a). The Dent Fault is the southern leg of the 'Penine Fault'.

Whilst Sedgwick procrastinated over writing up this field work, John Phillips described the more east-west Craven Faults that met the southern end of the Dent Fault (Phillips 1829). Only a few years later, Phillips (1836) was able to publish a structural synthesis map of northern England showing these faults and also the

Tynedale Fault to the north, all delimiting the stable Carboniferous core of the northern Pennines. The regional importance of this fault system is clear.

Map of faults in the Sedbergh area with the location of a shingled group of faults termed a strike-slip duplex

The Dent Fault after Sedgwick

The first mapping of the Dent Fault by the Geological Survey (e.g. Dakyns et al. 1891) delimited several component faults and yielded more accurate cross sections. Nearly a century later, mapping by Underhill et al. (1988) produced an improved cross-section and the recognition of strike-slip as well as reverse dip-slip displacements in the fault zone. A detailed resurvey of the Geological Survey Kendal and ad-

jacent sheets mapped out the subsidiary faults to the west of the main Dent Fault and showed that they define a shingled geometry (Woodcock and Rickards 2003; Thomas and Woodcock 2015), an internationally cited example of a strike-slip duplex.

A second important spinoff of the resurvey was a focus on the fault breccias in the Dent Fault. This work involved the establishment of the first non-genetic classification of fault breccias (Woodcock and Mort 2008) and a number of studies that have increased our understanding of the formation of fault breccias in general.

Two hundred years exactly since Adam Sedgwick began his researches in the Lakes and Dales, the Dent Fault continues to produce results of wide significance in ways that Sedgwick never even dreamed of.

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Malvern Rocks: geology in a Victorian health resort

HOGG field weekend in the Malvern Hills

HOGG's field weekend exploring Malvern and the Malvern Hills was its first since the pandemic restrictions were lifted. It was organised originally to take place in 2020 and was twice suspended due to lockdowns. But it was worth waiting for.

The Malvern Hills present a dramatic landscape as the dragon's back ridge rears above the surrounding country. It is particularly stunning from the eastern approaches across the level, low-lying Severn Plain, but it also dominates the skyline from the rolling Herefordshire hills to the west. Its close and frequent contours on the OS map suggest that it is bursting from the sheet. On aerial imagery its outline is clear as the bare boundaryless ridge contrasts with the surrounding patchwork of fields and small woods, (see p. 15). The ridge's core, the Precambrian Malvern Complex, separates Triassic strata on the east from Silurian strata to the west.

Throughout history, the Malvern Hills have attracted people – from early Britons exploiting its defensive potential to Georgian and Victorian visitors who came for the curative waters. The developments associated with the early spas coincided with the early Victorian interest in geology. The interpretations of the geology by early investigators reflected the various and developing conceptual models and the increasing expertise and professionalism of geologists through the nineteenth century. Over the weekend we visited many of the exposures observed by past geologists, led by organiser, Tim Carter, assisted along the way by local experts John Payne, Richard Edwards, and Moira Jenkins.

The weather was kind, sunny but not too warm, and excellent for walking. Our weekend began on Friday evening when Tim guided us around Malvern itself. The abundant local stone is found in retaining walls and buildings; the contrast between the hard irregular 'hill stone' of the Malvern Complex and the blocks and slabs of workable sedimentary rocks of the adjacent landscapes is immediately apparent. Tim led us to sites associated with Charles Darwin: the house he stayed in when he came initially seeking a water cure for himself and again two years later in a vain attempt to cure his young daughter, Annie, whose grave we also saw. We visited springs in the town centre: at the Elgar monument, at the source for Dr. Ralph Grindrod's Malvern water cures, and near where the Darwins stayed. Our evening walkabout concluded with a meal together at a popular Italian restaurant. It was a good opportunity to meet old friends and make new ones.

After supper, Tim issued the handouts, principally a 58 page booklet, *Malvern Rocks: geology in a Victorian health resort*, maps for the next days' walks, and a diagrammatic timeline showing the geological *dramatis personae*. This was inspired by Martin Rudwick's graphics linking individuals, their ideas and

associations and relative importance. It is an excellent way to visualise personal connections and conceptual development in a complex history.

Tim's booklet combines a historical narrative (pp 1-24) of the several figures who contributed to the development of the changing conceptual models of the Malvern Hills, with sections describing the significant changes in those concepts. The middle section is a chronological bibliography (pp25-31) of Malvern geological publications, while the final section lists the sites we visited, and includes accounts of how they were observed/interpreted by a sequence of earlier geologists (pp32-56). As the order that we actually visited the sites varied from the booklet, a two-page addendum updated and kept us together for the next two days.

Next morning, we met near the Wyche, a pass over the Malvern ridge. Wyche, in early English, relates to salt as in nearby Droitwich and Nantwich, where salt was mined. The old pack-horse route from the salt mines to South Wales traversed the Malverns through the Wyche. The present deep cutting was blasted by early nineteenth century turnpike engineers. (fig 1)

Figure 1 Wyche Cutting in Malvern Complex

Leonard Horner, FGS, visited the Wyche and provided the first detailed description in 1811 of what we now know as the Malvern Complex and mapped its boundaries to the east and west of the Wyche.

granite is the prevailing rock . . . red feldspar predominates . . . There is a considerable quantity of another rock, which seems to fill up the spaces that intervene between the masses of granite. It is chiefly argillaceous, of a dark olive-green colour, with an imperfect slaty structure (Horner, 1811)

Although Horner did not recognise the presence of an east-west fault zone through the Wyche, his article was recognised by later authors as the undisputed foundation for the work of later geologists. It also reflects the mineralogical focus of the early fellows of the Geological Society.

Following the national geological maps of Smith (1815) and Greenough (1820), general geological interest shifted to concentrate on stratified deposits and structures.

From near the Wyche, looking westward, we could see alternating farmed vales and wooded ridges expressing Silurian soft mudstones and hard limestones respectively. Descending westward along the old salt trail, here named the Purlieu, we followed a trail along a stream flowing westward through Park Wood. Several small exposures in the stream's bank and in adjacent small overgrown quarries revealed the same alternating sequence of Silurian rocks (fig. 2).

Murchison studied these beds in detail using characteristic fossils to distinguish between similar looking limestones and mudstones which he described in his *Silurian System* (1839). Murchison was particularly interested in the near vertical and overturned beds in the area and attributed them to the eruption of the Malvern ridge through overlying sedimentary rocks.

Figure 2 Silurian limestone in abandoned quarry beside the Purlieu section of the old salt trail.

From the end of the Purlieu it was a short drive to the Brewer's Arms, a community pub in West Malvern. Its garden was a welcome respite. From the pub, it was a short walk to the site of the Dingle, one of the few small valleys on the west side of the Malvern ridge. We were guided by John Payne, editor of *Herefordshire's Rocks and Scenery: a Geology of the County*.

The fledgling Geological Survey was interested in the economic potential of the limestones as a source of agricultural lime. John Phillips provided further insights (BGS memoir v2 pt1, 1848) dismissing Murchison's eruption theory. He noted a series of faulted uplifts on the west of the Malvern ridge leading to tilting and folding and recorded his sister's find – 'Miss Phillips' conglomerate' – lying at the base of Silurian limestones in unconformable contact with the Malvern complex. It clearly was not metamorphosed by contact with magma and it incorporates fragments of the Malvern complex and so certainly postdates it.

The Dingle is where Ann Phillips discovered 'her' conglomerate (fig.3). Unfortunately, the site of her discovery, Lower Dingle Quarry, has been infilled and the unconformity is now obscured by a small car park. John Phillips' sketch shows a near vertical contact of steeply dipping Silurian strata against the Malvern Complex. The conglomerate is a thin discontinuous deposit which is difficult to find.

Figure 3 Miss Phillips' Conglomerate

Further up the slope is a large overgrown quarry on two levels, Upper and Middle Dingle Quarries (fig.4), which are regularly cleared by Community Conservation Champions (CCCs) for students and amateur and professional geologists. Their studies have contributed enormously to the appreciation of the complexity of the Malvern Complex revealed in the detail of fault breccias, a thrust plane, dykes and the considerable lithological variability in the diorites, granites, and dolerites. Their predecessors: Horner, Phillips, Murchison, and others, would have been impressed.

Figure 4 Upper and Middle Dingle Quarries in Malvern Complex

Next, we visited the much larger Tank Quarry at the north end of the Malvern Hills ridge. Its very high faces, reaching

up to 300m, may only be viewed from a safe distance. Here we were met by Richard Edwards, another CCC, who with his team of volunteers not only revealed the Malvern Complex in several lower quarry exposures, but also organised interpretation boards and large boulder-sized examples of the several rock types forming the Complex.

Saturday afternoon was rounded off by a visit to Tim's home, Laburnum Cottage in North Malvern. It was a welcome break. Tim had laid out several maps, sections, and books which documented the history of geology and geotourism in the Malverns. Many thanks to Ann for the biscuits and cakes. We reassembled nearby a couple of hours later for dinner at a very popular venue, the Nag's Head.

On the Sunday morning, we met at the south end of the Malvern ridge, at Hollybush and Raggedstone Hills; the latter is so named as it has twin peaks as does Hollybush Hill. The defile between each pair of peaks was attributed to softer rocks along the axis of intense folding and shearing by Harvey Holl and Charles Callaway. John Payne again led us.

The geology here varied significantly from the north end of the Malverns. Greater complexity was recognised by Harvey Holl, a Worcester doctor. He was an accomplished geologist who had assisted Henry De la Beche in Southwest England in the nascent Geological Survey. Later, he worked for the Pennsylvania Geological Survey. In North America he became familiar with the old and complex metamorphic rocks of the Canadian Shield. He saw similarities with the Malvern Complex. The early Geological Survey had regarded the Malvern Complex as igneous at a time when metamorphism was viewed as a process solely operating on sedimentary rocks. Holl's experience led him to conclude that the core rocks of the Malvern Hills were probably metamorphosed granites similar in age to the rocks of the Canadian Shield then considered to be the oldest rocks on the earth's surface.

Holl identified an unconformable boundary of the Hollybush Sandstone overlying the Malvern Complex. The Hollybush Sandstone had fossil evidence of Cambrian age, thus pushing back the age of the Malvern Complex to pre-Cambrian (Holl, 1865). In the latter half of the 1800s, Holl was one of the first to bring foreign experience together with microscopic and geochemical studies to bear on the earliest Malvern developments, followed by Charles Callaway and Frank Rutley. Callaway was particularly interested in the changes to Malvern rocks that were present in shear zones; he suggested that minerals were reformulated under shear stress. His observations were controversial at the time. They implied that Lyell's concept of uniformitarianism could have its limits, with some processes occurring only in the early stage of the earth's existence.

South of Raggedstone Hill in the disused Chase End Quarry, near the hamlet of Whiteleaved Oak, John Payne showed us an instance of local tension associated with shearing. The limestone strata were stretched leaving gaps at joints. Returning to the cars northward through pastures, we

observed low ridges and patches of drier grey soil which were evidence of younger dolerite intrusions in the Cambrian mudstones.

We drove back to the GeoCentre near the Wyche for lunch. Here there was a good selection of geological pamphlets and books on the Malverns. In the afternoon we drove to British Camp (fig 5), an iron age hill fort at the north end of the southern part of the Malvern ridge. Here, we were met by Moira Jenkins who led us along the lowest of several earth ramparts from which there were clear views over the adjacent countryside.

Figure 5 British Camp iron age hill fort

Looking west, the sweeping curves of linear woodland on limestone ridges and alternating fields in clay vales were even clearer than the previous morning's views.

Looking north, the north part of the Malvern Ridge in the distance could be seen to follow a line offset to the east from the south part, where we were standing, by faulting (fig 6).

Figure 6 The north Malvern ridge on the horizon lies to the east of the south part of the ridge in the foreground. The offset is caused by an east-west transverse fault.

The view to the east revealed a rare instance of a basalt outcrop which formed a low, grey rounded ridge. Beyond it lies the agricultural patchwork of the Severn Plain and, on the

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John Henry

horizon, the hazy green line of the Cotswold escarpment (fig 7a).

Figure 7a Basalt ridge in middle distance, east of British Camp.

The grey outcrop is a Precambrian lava, the Warren House Volcanics. Closer inspection revealed it to be basalt with weakly defined pillow lavas, indicating deposition of lava underwater. A curious 18th century folly, Clutter's Cave, is excavated a short way into the outcrop (fig 7b).

Figure 7b Clutter's cave, an 18th century folly.

From the cave we walked back along the contour path below the hill fort to the car park where there were ice creams for all at the kiosk.

The weekend was all one could have wished for: splendid scenery, interesting historical insights into the interpretation of challenging geology, and convivial meals in good company. Apart from the excellent weather, we have much to thank the organiser for. Tim's knowledgeable leadership and authoritative field book, supplemented along the way by local experts, introduced us to numerous

hidden exposures, and the several nineteenth century geologists who unravelled the complex geological developments that formed the Malvern Hills.

On a personal note, I would like to thank Tim for reorganising his itinerary into shorter lengths between stops, and for guiding myself and another on a less challenging route around Raggedstone Hill when the others climbed over it. Thanks to Barrie Chacksfield for photos 1, 6 and 7b; the rest are my own.

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I have borrowed shamelessly from the following works to supplement my meagre field notes; however, any errors are my own.

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Figure 8 Plan of field site locations along the Malvern ridge. The red lines delineate the routes walked.

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Walking in the footsteps of Anglesey’s geological mapping pioneers

The geology of Môn (Anglesey)

HOGG’s field meeting held on 15-17 July 2022 brought a group of nine enthusiasts and three even more enthusiastic leaders to visit one of the UK’s more geologically complex regions.

Anglesey’s geology and how it was formed has been difficult to unravel. Since the early 19th century, a number of geologists have described the rocks and attempted to explain the events which have shaped the island; to a large extent through study of the coastal and other visible outcrops, and the general topography. This field trip was the opportunity to follow in the steps and thought processes of major pioneers of geological mapping: John Stevens Henslow (working there in 1822), Andrew Crombie Ramsay with Henry De la Beche (1849-51) and Edward Greenly (1920). The trip visited sites important to each of them in chronological order of their work, and illustrated the processes of their geological mapping techniques.

The trip was expertly led by Duncan Hawley (HOGG), Professor Cynthia Burek (GeoMôn), and Dr Rob Crossley (GeoMôn), to all of whom we are very grateful.

GeoMôn UNESCO Global Geopark

Meeting on the first evening at the GeoMôn UNESCO Global Geopark in Amlwch was the perfect introduction, with Cynthia Burek as guide. GeoMôn is one of 177 Global Geoparks in 46 countries, and one of 10 in the British Isles. Cynthia explained that the Geoparks are unified geographical areas where sites and landscapes of international geological significance are managed with an overall concept of protection, education and sustainable development. But they also aim to explore and develop the links between that underlying geology and all other aspects of the area’s natural, cultural and intangible heritages – geotourism, farming, local crafts and food. Importantly, they support geoconservation; the preservation of significant geodiversity sites to illustrate how the land has been shaped over the course of geological time.

GeoMôn Geopark Centre

GeoMôn Global Geopark is an area of spectacular geological interest, covering all of the geological periods except the Triassic, Jurassic and Cretaceous; more than a hundred rock types ranging from Precambrian blue and green schists, gneisses

and granite intrusions of the Mona Complex, to Carboniferous sandstones, and it is home to the oldest fossils in England and Wales. The whole landscape has been glaciated, with different rock types determining the extent of erosion, forming diverse soil types which contribute to biodiversity and local agricultural land use. In addition, Anglesey has since the bronze age been supporting a mining industry that was particularly prosperous in copper in the 19th century and today is prospecting also for zinc, lead, silver and gold.

Day 1: Holy Island and John Stevens Henslow

The first morning took the group to Holy Island in the north-west of Anglesey to illustrate the pioneering brilliance of the Revd John Stevens Henslow in interpreting the geology on the basis of little pre-existing knowledge, producing maps to cover the whole island by documenting rock exposures and following the strata between them.

Henslow’s Map of Anglesey (Duncan Hawley collection)

Henslow (1796-1861) was an outstanding geologist and botanist, now largely remembered for his influence on the young Charles Darwin. However early in his own career he made geological surveys of the Isles of both Wight and Man, and in 1821 he began surveying Anglesey – building on the limited information depicted in Greenough’s 1820 Geological Map of England and Wales. Henslow’s extraordinarily accurate observations and measurements were all the more impressive given the inadequately small-scale base maps he was using.

Rob Crossley took us along the south-eastern arm of Porth Dafarch to where a flat valley drained into the bay. As shown on Henslow’s map, the bay marks the contact between what he describes as quartz rock, with intensely folded strata and cleavage to the north-west and Precambrian or early Cambrian chlorite schist (ca. 545 Ma) to the east. Cutting across the rocks on both sides of the bay is a much younger, chemically rotting doleritic dyke (ca. 40 Ma), now known to contain olivine and pyroxene, and to extend all through Anglesey from the north-west to Caernarfon. The soft, chemically fertile dyke rock is expressed by green flat-floored

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Vivienne Kendall

valleys, but the valleys (and by inference the underlying dyke) on either side of the bay do not line up. We discussed whether this was due to offsetting after emplacement of the dyke or whether the dyke ‘doglegged’ to follow pre-existing cracks and joints along this major contact in the older rocks.

Rob Crossley points out the doleritic dyke

Moving north along the coast we followed the dyke through the Precambrian schist on the sea-cliff and up to South Stack. The

The dyke – centre, below the caravan park

dyke is significantly rotted but appears to have been injected in two or three stages. It shows an unambiguous ‘dogleg’ and in

sideways view, we saw columnar jointing. It is clear from Henslow’s Anglesey Memoir that he had distinguished cleavage and foliation from ordinary sedimentary bedding as early as 1821: drawing out basic geological principles at the age of only 24. He employed a compass-clinometer so he could document the angles of dips and strikes – seen in the drawing and diagram he drew from South Stack lighthouse. The folds are tectonic and Henslow demonstrated that they show at least three phases of folding. His observations of the different bedding planes here and in other parts of the island proved so complete and accurate that no less than Darwin, Lyell, Harker and Edward Greenly all remarked on it. Darwin commented:

Nothing seemed to give him so much enjoyment as drawing conclusions from minute observations. But his admirable memoir on the geology of Anglesea, [sic] shows his capacity for extended observations and broad views.

‘Contortions in the strata of the quartz rock at Holyhead mountain. Sketched from South Stack.’

Plate XV, Transactions of the Cambridge Philosophical Society, Vol. 1, Part 1, 1821. (Duncan Hawley collection)

Henslow also studied the occurrence of serpentinite in Anglesey. According to Greenough’s map, this extended in a continuous north-east to south-west band from Rhoscolyn to

Cemlyn Bay on the north coast. Henslow recognised that this continuous band was not accurate, and that the serpentinite formed a range of ‘tabular masses’ surrounded by chlorite schist. Henslow worked with information from local quarrymen and road-makers to establish its actual occurrence. Our group had difficulty locating serpentinite outcrops at a spot near Rhoscolyn due to massive overgrowth of gorse, but later found to our delight that the roughly paved track was in fact made of the green, greasy stone we had been searching for.

Serpentinite near Rhoscolyn – photographed in 2021 (note the gorse)
Photo R. Crossley

Llanelian, Ramsay and the deliberations of the Geological Survey

Starting from survey work carried out by Henry De la Beche in the late 1840s, the Geological Survey mapped Anglesey at one inch to the mile. With De la Beche was Andrew Crombie Ramsay (1814-1891) as senior surveyor. The rocks proved difficult to interpret, and the geological map was not published until 1852. Our group, led by Duncan Hawley, investigated the differences of opinion in that process while retracing part of Ramsay’s 1850 walk around Porth Eilian on Anglesey’s north-west coast toward Point Lynas (Trwyn Eilian) and then across the headland toward Porth y Corwgl.

Ramsay was a Scottish geologist whose map of Arran had so impressed Murchison that Murchison had recommended him to De la Beche as someone suitable for the Geological Survey. Ramsay visited the area in 1850 with Murchison, using Henslow’s map as a guide. The map indicated that some grits and conglomerates (of the ‘graptolitic slates’) were Old Red Sandstone, but this was doubted by Murchison and later repudiated by De la Beche.

In 1851 Ramsay returned with De la Beche, who advised Ramsay to take particular notice of conglomerates as indicating the base of a sedimentary sequence and possibly an unconformity. Conglomerates had already been found near Llyn Padarn and next to the Menai Strait near Bangor, and the strike of the latter was towards Anglesey. There was therefore some prospect of finding the base of the Cambrian, lying on the schists, somewhere north of Bangor, in Anglesey. So our group set about looking for evidence of conglomerates on the rocky cliff edge to the east of the Point Lynas headland.

However, De la Beche was taken ill late in 1851 and the area our group had reached, north of Porth Corwgl, was the last spot he surveyed. The white line on Ramsay’s map represents Carmel Head

HOGG members tracing the footsteps of Ramsay and De la Beche

fault; the site of Carmel Head Thrust where gneisses, now known to be Precambrian and almost certainly the oldest rocks in Wales, were forced up over younger Ordovician deposits.

Ramsay interpreted the red and green rocks there as ‘altered Cambrian’, i.e. he held they had been metamorphosed by granite intrusion. De la Beche had been considering that the metamorphics predated the Cambrian, but it was Ramsay’s view that was presented in the Geological Survey map and related publications. Ramsay held that Anglesey metamorphics were ‘altered Cambrian/Silurian’, and so he bundled together the many varieties of schists, gneisses, tufts, jaspers, spilites, phyllites, and even different bedded rocks near Holyhead under this label. The geological map that resulted was therefore relatively simple: showing granite, greenstone and serpentine; Lower Silurian rocks (later renamed as Ordovician); Old Red Sandstone; Carboniferous and the ‘altered Cambrian’.

NE part of Geological Survey Map 78 N. Anglesey, 1852.
Courtesy David Rumsey Map Collection

Ramsay’s idea was that the purple and green slate across the Menai Strait were the same. He argued that

...there is no reason to doubt that the green and purple foliated rocks on the Anglesea shore of the Menai are the same Cambrian strata more thoroughly metamorphosed.

He was reasoning that the metamorphism on Anglesey was caused by alteration around the large granitic/gneissose body occupying the core of the island surrounded by ‘Cambrian’ beds (now known to be Ordovician), similar to igneous quartz-porphyry ‘ribs’ seen on the nearby mainland, which he believed were connected sub-surface. In this thinking Ramsay may have been influenced by what he observed in his early experiences on Arran, where quartz-porphyry rocks are juxtaposed with granite bodies. Ramsay observed the igneous body was ‘not an intrusive mass in the ordinary sense’, arguing the alteration was by a process now known as metasomatism.

...the solid porphyry itself is nothing but the result of the alteration of the stratified masses carried a stage further into the region of that kind of absolute fusion that in so many regions resulted in the formation of granites, syenites and other rocks, commonly called intrusive.

Accordingly, Ramsay believed that on Anglesey a considerable portion of what he considered as Lower Silurian

and Cambrian rocks had been metamorphosed into gneiss and mica schist, hence ‘Altered Cambrian/Silurian’ on the map. Thus, no pre-Cambrian rocks were admitted to Anglesey and the Survey remained wedded to the influence of Murchison’s Silurian ‘empire’.

However Ramsay’s interpretation began to unravel in subsequent years when ‘amateur’ geologists provided evidence that there was no conformable transition across the Menai Strait and discovered unconformities separating black beds of Cambrian from underlying beds that reason demanded were pre-Cambrian. It took 40 years before the Survey admitted their error of interpretation. In his 1891 Presidential address to the Geological Society, Archibald Geikie conceded that Ramsay had been mistaken to infer that the schists and gneisses of Anglesey were only metamorphosed Silurian and Cambrian beds. In fairness to Ramsay, there were undoubtedly time constraints as he was obliged to publish the map quickly, and this may have compromised its accuracy. However the stage was set for Edward Greenly to undertake his detailed re-mapping of Anglesey.

Day 2: Ffynnon Eilean – A sacred place for Edward and Annie Greenly

A short walk eastward along the north coast from Amlwch Port enabled us to follow the very significant path of Edward and Annie Greenly on the day of completion of his one-inch geological map of Anglesey in October 1910. However, it was only in 1919 that the two-volume Memoir was published, with the map following in 1920. Together they were the product of 25 years’ labour, of which more than 15 were devoted to fieldwork.

Edward Greenly (1861-1951) became interested in geology in his teens, following a visit to the Lake District. He studied chemistry at University College London where his interest in petrology was further inspired by Professor Thomas Bonney. A chance meeting with Alexander Green, then professor of geology at Yorkshire College (now the University of Leeds) led to three weeks spent mapping together and a recommendation that Greenly should join the Geological Survey. He spent until 1895 working with John Horne and Benjamin Peach in mapping the North-West Highlands, learning and refining his techniques in difficult terrain.

Duncan and Cynthia outlined the critical part in Greenly’s work played by his wife, Annie. Although early sweethearts, they were only married in 1891 and they lived together in remote parts of Scotland while he continued mapping and Annie applied herself to learning as much as she could about geology. She also concerned herself with the logistics of their trips; for example, in Greenly’s words:

More than one geologist, Clough himself, alas included, has been killed while examining railway cuttings. When the author was examining cuttings in Anglesey, Annie Greenly always came with him as a train-watcher and with her at the top of the bank, he was able to concentrate on the geology.

But Annie's influence extended far beyond practicalities. Greenly was aware that his mapping did not match the very high standard set by Clough, and was concerned at the difficulties of recording complex metamorphosed rocks. Annie encouraged him to record only what could be seen. He wrote later that she said:

Let Clough be your model in precision, but do not model him in style. Found your style on nature's curves. Watch these wherever you can and where you cannot see them, feel them. To be true, a map must be beautiful.

This led to Greenly's use of a green line to outline rock exposures with precision. For the first time it was clear on a geological map which lines were visible and which inferred. He wrote:

It has been supposed that my inspiration was the wonderful mapping of Clough. Such, however, was not the case. True, when once I began to aspire [to a higher standard of geological mapping] it was the maps of Clough which became my models. But the initial source of my inspiration was no other than Annie Greenly.' (Greenly's emphasis.)

Greenly left the Geological Survey in 1894, but wanted to continue mapping and decided to address the geology of Anglesey, as much of it contained metamorphosed rocks which were familiar to him from the Highlands. His fieldwork there occupied the next 15 years.

The north coast between Amlwch Port and Ffynnon Eilian where we now stood, is a rugged moor edged by inaccessible sea-cliffs. Greenly's six-inch field map shows every rock formation within his green lines.

Greenly's field map. – Amlwch Port Moor
From Greenly and Williams (1930), *Methods in Geological Surveying*.
(Duncan Hawley collection).

Every formation is part of the Mona complex: the pale green (designated 'country rock') represents the schists; the dark green is spillite lavas, now partly schistose, and the russet brown is jaspers and phyllites. Greenly emphasised later that the outcrops of jaspery beds were plotted only as far as they could actually be seen and that the map had not been inferred from any theory of tectonics. The forms of the outcrops were explained by the beds being cut by innumerable thrusts at extremely acute angles to the bedding; after which thrusts as well as bedding had been folded on rapid minor isoclinal.

Ffynnon Eilian, close to a holy well with alleged mystical powers, was indeed a special place for the Greenlys. After 15 years of work, Annie had asked her husband if she would ever live to see the completion of the map. She asked him to send her a postcard when he was sure he had less than a day's work remaining, so that she could be there. On 8 October 1910, she came out by train and they walked to Ffynnon Eilian 'between the crags, winding along secluded paths, with satisfaction in our hearts that all this country had been mapped'. Greenly worked a little, mapping the last crag and a zone of pale haematite and jasper with the last green line. He closed his map-case and embraced Annie; he recorded later that Ffynnon Eilian was to him a Sacred Site.

Ffynnon Eilian: Edward Greenly's 'Sacred Site'
Photo from Greenly (1938), *A Hand in Time* (Vol.1)
(Duncan Hawley collection).

After some further fieldwork, including a trip to the Skerries, the Greenlys concentrated on completion of the one-inch map and *The Geology of Anglesey*, the two-volume memoir. Annie made a further major contribution by compiling the index to the memoir; documenting 1879 subjects on individual slips of paper: a massive task that justly deserved its preservation in the National Library of Wales. It is interesting that in taking the maps and the memoir by rail to London for publication, they insured them for £1000; they found on arrival that a railway superintendent and a Scotland Yard detective had been detailed to accompany them.

Margaret Wood

It was a great privilege for the group to be invited to visit Dr Margaret Wood in her delightful and endlessly fascinating cottage. Not only the founder of GeoMôn in 2009, she has co-authored the first full account of Anglesey's geology since Greenly and established the international reputation of Anglesey's geodiversity. The visit also provided the opportunity for us to examine copies of Margaret's two-volume *Geology of Anglesey*, Cynthia's copy of Greenly's *A Hand through Time* and also a copy of Greenly's 1920 map of Anglesey's geology owned by Barrie Chacksfield. We were most grateful for this, and for the very warm welcome (and chocolate!) that Margaret gave us.

Graves of two of Anglesey’s pioneer geologists

Nearing the end of our time in Anglesey, we visited the graves of three of our study subjects: Sir Andrew Ramsay and Edward and Annie Greenly.

Sir Andrew Ramsey died in 1891 and is buried in the churchyard of St Sadwrn’s Church, Llandudwr. Appropriately for a geologist deeply interested in glaciation, his tombstone is a large glacial erratic of Carboniferous limestone with numerous fossil fragments, originally found in Beaumaris

The erratic was probably moved by the mid-Irish Sea ice stream in its flow north-west to south-east. Ramsay was the first to suggest this direction of ice movement in Anglesey.

Photo Duncan Hawley

Annie Greenly, nine years older than her husband, died in 1927. Not until 1951 did Edward Greenly join her in the churchyard of St Cristiolus, Llangristiolus.

Their grave is made from red Balmoral granite, from Finland, composed of red orthoclase. It features an open book and unusually records Edward Greenly’s DSc and his Fellowship of the Geological Society. The book shows his details on the left; Annie’s on the right. The inscription – ‘Reunited’ – reflects their devotion.

Llandwyn Island – Greenly’s mélangé

Unfortunately, it was not possible to visit the last planned port of call in our field meeting; many factors conspired against us. But Llandwyn Island, felt by some to be the pinnacle in Anglesey’s geological story, is mentioned here for the sake of others who may be able to visit Anglesey at a later date.

Llandwyn is a complete account on a small scale of a plate tectonic story: the formation of rocks at a mid-ocean ridge, the accumulation of sediments on the ocean floor, and their burial and metamorphism as plates collided and some sank into a deep ocean trench.

On the landward (NW) side of the island are newly exposed pillow lavas, formed on the seabed some 580 Ma, trapping iron-rich sand and mud between the pillows and transforming the sand by heat into jasper, and mud into green epidote. Further south and onto the island are successively vertical sedimentary mudstones and alternating bands of jasper and green chlorite-rich mudstones. And finally at Porth Twr beach is the famous mélangé first described by Greenly and formerly known as crush breccia. The mixture of red chert, pink and white quartzite and green schist results from deformation, chemical alteration and metamorphism.

The rock ‘melange’ at Porth Twr Bach
cc-by-sa/2.0 - © Gordon Hatton - geograph.org.uk/p/5460444

The rocks from the ocean floor were dragged into a deep trench as one plate subducted beneath the other, then more recently cracks were filled with lava to form dolerite dykes. Llandwyn is the world type-location for mélangé deposits.

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(All photos, unless stated otherwise, by V. Kendall)

True to Nature: Open-air Painting in Europe 1780-1870Ger Luijten *et al.*,

Paul Holberton Publishing 2020

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280pp

The pursuit of active fieldwork by geologically minded naturalists in the late 18th century coincided with an important development in the history of painting – namely the portraiture of landscape *en plein air*, which revolutionized the way natural landscapes were viewed. This raises the question of whether the art was informed by the science or *vice versa*?

Some answers are provided by *True to Nature: Open-air Painting in Europe 1780-1870*, an exhibition staged in Washington and Paris; before ending, this summer, at the Fitzwilliam Museum, Cambridge. Even if you missed this fascinating exhibition, the lavishly illustrated book compensates to a considerable degree with 13 essays covering topics ranging from ‘Making their Mark: The Handling of Paint in *Plein Air* Sketches’ and ‘Painting in Nature’ to ‘Rocks and Grottoes’ and ‘Volcanoes’.

For the painters, the aim was to try to capture fresh and spontaneous transcriptions of natural scenes in two dimensions using materials that could be carried into the field. As the Introduction points out, from the late 18th century, artists increasingly took to the field to practise ‘the Enlightenment ideal of observing reality first-hand’ while ‘objectively gathering empirical data’. To do this successfully was no mean feat. Carrying even the minimum equipment and manipulating paint while contending with locations from rocky coasts to high alps and volcanoes as well as the vicissitudes of the weather was not for the faint hearted. In 1824, Auguste-Xavier Leprince (1799-1826) portrayed two artists high in the snowy Alps of Susten in the Swiss Canton of Uri, laden with backpacks, easels, ice picks and umbrellas and still sketching as they struggled over a mountain pass.

The exhibition shows that artists across Europe became adept at rapidly distilling their understanding and experiences of Nature and translating complex phenomena into compelling works of art. A great variety of natural landscapes were portrayed from Anicet Lemonnier’s (1743-1824) *Vesuvius in Eruption, 1779*, (cat. no. 47) to Eugene Isabey’s (1803-1886) *Rocks at Cran aux Oenfs near Calais* in 1832 (cat. no. 32) and in 1850, the Dane Vilhelm Kyhn’s (1819-1903) *Landscape in the Haute-Savoie, with an Artist working in the Open Air* (cat. no. 36). Many if not most of these works were painted as *aides-memoires* for works to be finished in the studio for exhibition or sale. Although few scientists will have been privy to these preliminary sketches, many will have seen, and been influenced by, the finished works, especially those depicting active volcanism.

Vesuvius, with its proximity to Naples and busy Mediterranean sea-routes, was the most accessible of active European volcanoes. Beginning in 1631, there were successive violent eruptive episodes in 1794, 1822, 1834, 1850 and 1872. Intrepid and often foolhardy naturalists, ‘tourists’

and artists traipsed up the slopes to gawp at the spectacular show. The artists were on hand to fulfil the demand for a visual record of the drama and their *en plein air* works captured the natural firework display and led to the production of numerous finished works and cheaper reproductions.

As Janet Munro of the Fitzwilliam Museum points out, it was Pierre-Henri de Valenciennes (1750-1819), who, in his influential *Éléments de perspective pratique* (1799-1800), drew the attention of artists to ‘the awe-inspiring sight of a volcanic eruption, “the most terrible and the most magnificent spectacle” that Nature had to offer’. Munro cites examples of ‘an entire generation of European painters ...[who] made a speciality of painting volcanoes’ including Pierre-Jacques Volaire (1729-1799), Jacob Phillip Hackert (1737-1807) Joseph Wright of Derby (1734-1797) and Pietro Fabris (1740-1792), to which list can be added the British artists Thomas Jones (1742-1803) and John Robert Cozens (1752-1797).

However, it was perhaps Sir William Hamilton (1730-1803), diplomat, antiquarian, member of the Society of Dilettanti, friend of Nelson and Envoy Extraordinary to the Kingdom of the Two Sicilies (1764 – 1800), who was the foremost promoter of Vesuvius as an exemplar of volcanic activity.

Hamilton used his ringside seat in Naples to produce several accounts of the volcanism including his 1772 *Observations on Mount Vesuvius, Mount Etna, and other volcanos* and, in 1776, a collection of letters on volcanoes, entitled *Campi Phlegraei*. These works were illustrated by a large number of dramatic hand-coloured engravings based on paintings by Pietro Fabris which stimulated a wider interest and led to London exhibitions of the original artwork in 1768 and 1772. In the early 19th century eminent scientists such as Alexander von Humboldt (1769-1859), Alexandre Brongniart (1770-1847), Charles Lyell (1788-1865) and Humphry Davy (1778-1829) all studied Vesuvius.

As well as a feast for the eyes, *True to Nature* provides much food for thought about the relationship between art and geological science in the late 18th and 19th centuries.

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The Evolution of Paleontological Art (Memoir 218)

Renee M. Clary, G.D. Rosenberg and D.C. Evans, (eds.)
 Geological Society of America 2022 £43.00
 ISBN 978-0-813712-18-5 275pp

This collection of twenty-nine papers is essential reading for anyone interested in paleoart. Growing from a GSA conference at the University of Indiana in 2018, the differing approaches adopted by individual contributors offer a variety of analytical methodologies. Between them they cover work in a diversity of media: broadsheets, specialist monographs, school textbooks and wallcharts, the walls of natural history, fine art and university geology museums: a range that extends from cutting-edge research papers to ancient rock paintings!

The papers span both time and space. Although most address paleontological art from the early 19th century onwards, we learn that extinct animal tracks feature in prehistoric art (Goldstein and Getty), and we are also reminded that an early engagement with fossils may have contributed at some atavistic level to Antique art, myths and biblical stories (Bakker, Rosenberg and Burke).

On more familiar territory for many HOGG members is a paper on De la Beche's *Duria Antiquior*, generally acknowledged to be the first visual reconstruction of a former world (Sharpe and Clary). This adds fresh insights to Martin Rudwick's seminal discussion in *Scenes from Deep Time* (1992). Bork provides a timely reminder of the importance of Brongniart and Cuvier in Paris in establishing the use of art as a fundamental tool in knowledge-building. Several authors (e.g., Lewis, Wigley, J. and L. Diemer) use the book projects of particular authors and their artists to explain the intricacies of different reproductive techniques. These papers show the value of re-visiting works from the earliest stages of a modern understanding of different periods of the earth's history and emphasise how important has been the relationship between artists and those commissioning and informing their artwork. Such relationships could go horribly wrong, as in Benjamin Waterhouse Hawkins' planned work for the city of New York, scuppered by mafia-style thuggery (Peck and Rowland), or could be fraught, as Clary shows in her paper on the work of the artist Charles R. Knight and the museum staff at the Field Museum in Chicago.

Moving to the present, Clary (geoscientist and museum director), Rowan (artist) and Funderbunk (professor of art) write about their own recent collaboration on murals for the Dunn-Seiler Museum of Geosciences at Mississippi State to demonstrate what an equitable relationship between client, specialists and artists can achieve. The inclusion of photographs and visitor reports shows how their murals have

transformed the museum into an exciting and engaging learning environment. Another artist, Pecsics, writes about his work with geologists on recent excavation projects at Hungary's Eötvös Loránd University. His illustrations of reconstructions of theropod dinosaurs provide further insight into the fruitful collaborations now taking place.

My own interest in schools and universities as contexts for artists' work is well served. Elliott's paper reveals that the Pestalozzian principles of combining training in art and experiential learning were crucial for early geological survey publications produced at New Harmony, Indiana; and Wannier tells how, in the mid- 20th century, another Swiss, Manfred Reichel, combined the roles of artist, geologist and university teacher to produce an extraordinary array of educational material. Rowland relates

how the discovery of some unloved educational wallcharts in Las Vegas led him to uncover the story of their origin: commissioned in the 1950s by Austrian palaeontologist E. Thenius from the artist F. Zerritsch. Rowland was even able to discuss the charts' original conception with the 97-year-old Thenius himself. However, the precarious life of such items, once no longer regularly used, is demonstrated by Parkes' paper on the large charts by the Irish geological surveyor and artist Du Noyer and by Brice's work on the models and casts produced by Ward's of Rochester NY for Cornell.

Jovanovic-Kruspel and Harzhauser's paper on the programme of visual education incorporated into the fabric of Vienna's Natural History Museum (ca.1880-90) provides a welcome reminder that paleoart is firmly rooted in its own time. The designers' concern for scientific accuracy is not in doubt, but the museum's decor is suffused with stylistic and cultural references that anchor it firmly to its period and that are fundamental to its significance today. As the editors (Clary et al) stress in their introduction, no apology should be given for the fact that the reconstructions of former worlds may not align with today's state of knowledge and understanding.

I am grateful to the sponsors who made this publication possible. My reservations concern the quality of the paper used, which seems unsuited to the high-definition reproduction of some images, and the lack of an index or any biographical information which would help to contextualise the wide range of approaches taken by the different authors. Notwithstanding this, the range, variety and content of the papers make them truly fascinating. I would recommend this volume to anyone with an interest in the history of geology, science museums, art in science and science communication.

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Introduction

In the 19th Century, artists often sketched and painted the landscape in the very same remote parts of the UK that those in the vanguard of the empirical geologists were studying.

One such artist was Thomas Compton. We know very little about his early life, but he must have been born in the 1780s and died sometime after 1835 (before census records) (Table 1).

Compton travelled through North Wales in the early part of the century. His collected work has been published by the Reverend Canon David Yerburg. Whilst the artist's original work included studies of many iconic landscapes of North Wales including Snowdon, Harlech Castle and the Vale of Llangollen, this paper reviews two paintings of landscapes where the underlying geology comprises the end of the Ordovician Period, the Hirnantian. Geologically notable as a consequence of the short-lived global 'icehouse' and a coeval mass extinction, the rocks of this period, described for many years as the 'Bala' rocks, find themselves at the heart of the famous Murchison (1792-1871) – Sedgwick (1785-1873) controversy, over what was to be considered 'Cambrian' (sensu Murchison) or 'Silurian' (sensu Sedgwick). This debate was ultimately settled, posthumously to both protagonists, by the insertion of the Ordovician Period by Lapworth. Rocks of this age, the latest in the Ordovician, are termed 'Hirnantian' by stratigraphers globally, as a recognition of the diagnostic 'Hirnantia Fauna' originally described from Cwm Hirnant, near Bala.

Following his work in the field, Compton produced a series of original drawings which were prepared as hand-coloured aquatints for subsequent publication. Compton recorded the Hirnantian-based landscape in his pictures of Bwlch y Groes (Pass of the Cross) and Aberconwy (Figure 1). These paintings are now reviewed against our modern understanding of the local geology.

Table 1. Thomas Compton activities with locations

Date	Location	Activity
~1803	Berry Head, Torbay	Possibly engaged in undertaking survey work
	Hilsea, Hampshire	Possibly engaged in undertaking survey work
1803-4	Lundy Island	Surveying for the Royal Ordnance
1806	Woolwich Royal Military Academy	Assistant 'Drawing Master for Ground'
1814-1815	Wales	Touring
1820	Woolwich Royal Military Academy	in receipt of a pension following retirement
1826	Elizabeth College Guernsey	Master for 'Drawing and Surveying'
1835	Elizabeth College Guernsey	Retires as teacher

Notes to Table 1

1803-1804, this work was subsequently found to be inaccurate, and the survey of Lundy was repeated some years later, although whether the error was Compton's or those of the officers higher up in the ranks is somewhat uncertain.

1821 (September), recorded to be in receipt of a pension equivalent to a sum of £139 10s following retirement after 17 years of service as 'Assistant Drawing Master for Ground (Royal Military Academy, Woolwich)' (Anon 1821)

1826, joined the staff of Elizabeth College Guernsey, where he taught as 'Master for Drawing and Surveying' (Jacob 1830). Undertook a series of sketches of Guernsey subsequently published as the 'Moss Prints' (see Figure 4).

1835 – retires from Elizabeth College with the intention of returning to the mainland

Figure 1: Locations: AbC – Aberconwy; ByG – Bwlch y Groes; CHN – Cwm Hirnant

Historical Context

The late 18th and early 19th Century saw considerable advances in the social, economic, scientific and engineering fields, including the expansion of canals, railways and roads spearheaded by Telford (1757-1834) and Brunel (1806-1859). The threat of invasion from the Continent was a major concern to which the political establishment responded by establishing the Ordnance Survey – with an initial remit to survey the South Coast for defences against the threat from France – and, in 1806, by setting up a purpose-built Officer training College at Woolwich.

There was a growing interest in the natural history of the British landscape among the leisured classes in this post-enlightenment society. This was associated with a taste for landscape painting that brought to middle-class drawing rooms a plethora of tourist guides to the remoter areas of the British Isles and many prints glorifying the grandeur of areas like the Lake District and the Scottish and Welsh Highlands.

Although Compton's visit to North Wales predated much of the mid-19th century formal mapping that has contributed so much to the geological literature, he probably planned his itinerary using Pennant's 1778 *A Tour in Wales*.

Year (AD)	Thomas Compton	Historical Context	Geological Context
1780	Born?	1778 – Pennant’s <i>Tour of Wales</i> published	1780 – Jean Etienne Guettard – <i>Atlas et description mineralogiques de la France</i>
1790		1789 - French Revolution	1788 - Hutton <i>Theory of the Earth</i>
1795		1790 – 1800 – JMW Turner’s tours in Wales	1794 – Erasmus Darwin <i>Zoonomia</i>
1800	1804 – Surveying Lundy	1801 - Act of Union creates United Kingdom	1798- Malthus <i>An Essay on the Principle of Population</i>
1805	1806 – joins staff at RMA (Woolwich)	1806 – RMA occupies new premises at Woolwich	1807 – Geological Society of London inaugurated
1810	1813-1814 Painting Tour of Wales	1812 – Napoleon invades Russia	1811 –Cuvier & Brongniart <i>Essais sur la geographie mineralogique des environs du Paris</i>
1815		1815 – Battle of Waterloo	1815 – William Smith’s Geological Map of England and Wales
1820	1821 –Listed as receiving RMA pension	1819 – Peterloo Massacre in Manchester	1820 – Buckland – <i>Vindiciae Geologicae</i>
1825	1826 - Joins staff at Elizabeth College, Guernsey	1826 – Telford’s Conway Road Bridge 1829 - Catholic Emancipation	1825 – Cuvier <i>Discours sur les revolutions de la surface du globe</i>
1830	‘Moss Prints’	1833 - Abolition of Slavery Bill	1830 - Lyell <i>Principles of Geology</i> (Vol. 1) 1831 Sedgwick & Darwin in Wales
1835	1835 - Retires from teaching	1837 - Succession of Queen Victoria	1834 – Sedgwick & Murchison joint tour in Wales 1835 – Founding of the Geological Survey 1835 – Concepcion earthquake – witnessed by Darwin
1840		1841 – GWR line to Bristol opened	1840 - Agassiz <i>Etudes sur les Glaciers</i>
1850	Dies?	1848 – Stephenson’s Conway Railway bridge built 1850 - Establishment of pre-Raphaelite Brotherhood	1852 – Barrande <i>Systeme Silurien du Centre de la Boheme</i>
1875		1874 – Paris exhibition –birth of ‘impressionism’	

Table 2. Selected chronology relating to Thomas Compton with the historical and geological context

Geological Context

The pair of Compton’s paintings reviewed here reflect a somewhat subdued relief associated with the sedimentary rocks of the latest Ordovician ‘Hirnantian’ Stage. These rocks display a field record of the first recognised Phanerozoic glacial episode, and the second most influential mass extinction of the Phanerozoic. Compton’s visit predated any concept of the Hirnantian, the rocks originally being termed the ‘Bala’ Series.

The rocks at Aberconwy are seen at outcrop along the western shore of the Conwy Estuary, and in the Conwy Castle Sandstone Formation. This resistant stratum forms a ridge of bedrock on which Conwy Castle was built. Stone for the construction work was brought from quarries in a further outcrop of Hirnantian rock beneath Deganwy Castle on the Eastern bank of the estuary.

The competent Conway Castle Grit is absent at Bwlch y Groes, with the coeval rocks in this area being either:

1. the Hirnant Limestone (a distinctive oolitic limestone, often associated with the brachiopod-dominated Hirnantia Fauna), or
2. the Calettwr Quartzite

Compton’s eye for geological detail

Compton undertook his training some years before the scientific method was rigorously applied to geology (Table 2). It is a shame because in his work we see that Compton had an intuitive understanding of the rocks that mould the overlying soils and landscape. He picks up minor breaks of

Figure 2a: Compton’s view of Bwlch y Groes

Figure 2b: Bwlch y groes (View point at SH913226 – looking south)
Photo Keith Nicholls

Thomas Compton & the Hirnantian rocks

slope, and accurately plots their course across country. In his painting of Bwlch-y-Groes it is possible to identify the boundary between the Cwm-yr-Aethnen Shales and the overlying Llandovery strata by a gentle change in slope angle near the left hand (eastern) valley bottom. One weakness, however, is apparent. This is Compton's seeming misunderstanding of the gross structural bedding arrangements within the rock mass. The Bwlch-y-Groes painting appears to show a steeply dipping bedding structure that is not present in the rock mass. Bedding dips at a much shallower angle, but it may be that rather than indicating a failure to understand the interplay between bedding angle and subsequent weathered slope surface angles, Compton is attempting to offer a more majestic 'impression' of the Cambrian Mountains to his audience. In so doing it would appear that, to steepen the appearance of the slopes, he has steepened up the bedding that defines the major structural fabric of the rock mass.

Figure 3a: Compton's view of Aberconwy

Figure 3b: Aberconwy (looking south from SH784786.) note Stephenson's railway bridge (1848) and Telford's suspension bridge (1826) to left – both post-date Compton's work. Photo Keith Nicholls

There is less detail apparent from the view of Conway Castle despite the absence of the road and rail bridges subsequently built by Stephenson and Telford, which nowadays obscure the toe of the Benarth Hill. However, he has determined the boundary line between the Conway Castle

Keith Nicholls & Cynthia Burek

Grit and the overlying Gyffin Shales, as it tracks westward from the Castle outcrop itself, by a gentle break of slope in the hillside.

Compton's artwork

Compton's artwork is intriguing. His later work, exemplified by the Guernsey Moss Prints (Figure 4), shows his ability to represent accurately figures and buildings set within their landscape. Indeed, with his background in surveying for the military, we might anticipate that his scaling, and technical reproduction skills should be good.

Figure 4: 'Moss Print' of 1830 – Royal College of Elizabeth, Guernsey by Thomas Compton
Royal Collection Trust / © Her Majesty Queen Elizabeth II 2022

However, such skill is not always demonstrated, and it is frequently apparent that Compton takes liberties with his figures. It seems that the figures are introduced almost as an afterthought; they are certainly not the centrepieces of his works. In the Bwlch-y-Groes painting, the figures appear grossly undersized with respect to the scenery in which they are set.

Whether this is a deliberate intention on Compton's part to 'up-scale' the grandeur of the landscape by depicting items of known scale smaller than they are, or simply reflects additional composition painted by the artist after the fact, cannot be ascertained.

The work of the artist with respect to the figures is simple almost to the point of being 'primitive' and the viewer is reminded of Lowry's 'matchstick men'. Yerbergh's collection of Compton's work was sub-titled *An artistic impression* and it seems that Compton did not work in the prescriptive method that subsequently became associated with the Pre-Raphaelites, but owed more to Turner, and the later impressionist movement.

Keith Nicholls

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This paper was originally read at the *Appreciating physical landscapes: Geotourism 1670-1970* HOGG conference in 2012.

Nina Morgan outlines the geological origins of the Oxford University Museum of Natural History.

Sir Henry Wentworth Acland
(Wellcome Collection)

The Oxford University Museum of Natural History (OUMNH) is now celebrated as one of the most important Gothic revival buildings of the 19th century. Two of the driving forces behind the Museum project were the medic Dr Henry Acland (1815-1900), and the geologist John Phillips (1800-1874).

Phillips, nephew of William Smith (1769-1839), the ‘Father of English Geology’, became the first Professor of Geology at Oxford in 1856, and was appointed as the first Keeper of the new University Museum in 1857, posts he held until his death. Phillips was a great polymath, and his interests in architecture, decoration, education and geology are reflected in the Museum building today.

John Phillips
(Wiki Commons)

Science from the start

The design was chosen by a competition held in 1854. This was eventually won by the Irish firm, Deane and Woodward. Benjamin Woodward (1816-1861), then only 38 years old, served as the chief architect. From the beginning, the object of the Museum founders was to teach science. And its design was based on Acland’s idea that ‘no ornament should be employed which had no significance with reference to the object of the building.’ Geology, and John Phillips, played a key role in achieving this goal.

Like Acland, Phillips was keen that the decoration throughout the Museum building itself should serve as a teaching tool. As a result, one of the many notable features of the Museum building is the widespread use of coloured stone as a decorative feature, both on the exterior and interior of the building. As Phillips himself noted:

Though the stone of which the Museum is built, and the marbles which are employed in the internal decoration, can hardly be regarded as part of the collections of rocks, they must be included among the objects to which the student of geology should devote some attention; and were indeed in part selected for the purpose of adding to the illustrations of that science.

The 127 polished stone columns, composed of a wide range of British and Irish stones and topped by carved capitals representing botanical specimens, are among the most striking features of the Museum interior – and in geological terms the most instructive.

The Museum Interior today

© Mike Tomlinson

As the ‘radical parson’, the Reverend William Tuckwell, wrote in his 1901 book, *Reminiscences of Oxford* ‘The shafts of the interior arches, representing in their sequence the succession of British rocks, sent us into the Radcliffe Library for the mastery of geological classification’. It has been delighting geologists and the public ever since.

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The title page of Phillips’s 1863 pamphlet ©OUMNH

A Story in Stone: The Geology of the Oxford University Museum of Natural History Building

has been written by HOGG member and *GeoHistories* contributor, Nina Morgan, together with the one-time Curator of Geology at the OUMNH, Philip Powell, specifically to describe the richness of British geology displayed in the building. The book shows that this magnificent Museum, which opened to the public in 1860, continues to provide a wonderful introduction to both science and the geology of Britain in a way that is accessible to visitors of all types – it also remains a feast for the eye.

For more information about this book or to order a copy, priced £18 + £3.50 for p&p., please visit www.gravestonegeology.uk, or email Nina at nina.morgan@cooptel.net.

Trinity College Cambridge, 19th April 2022

Martin Rudwick is one of the leading figures in the history of earth sciences. His influence has spread far beyond this and contributed a deeper understanding of how knowledge is developed in both sciences and humanities. His work has contributed new ways of studying and presenting history and has strengthened our appreciation that the spiritual and scientific facets of reasoning have been, in most situations, synergistic and free from antagonism.

I first came across Martin as an undergraduate when I took a course in geology. Still at that time a palaeontologist specialising in brachiopods, Martin became my supervisor. Then, in retirement, I developed an interest in the history of geology and quickly discovered that he had written some of the most profound and informative books in the field, notably *Worlds before Adam*, *Bursting the Limits of Time* and *The Great Devonian Controversy*. When I heard about this conference I just had to attend. It proved to be both memorable and mind-stretching. Speakers and attendees came from around the world, with some missing most of a night's sleep to join on Zoom.

It is difficult to summarise what was a rich and varied day, with contributions from those who had benefited from Martin's advice and support or used his writings and methods of working as the basis for their own studies. Several themes stood out: the use of analogy as a tool for explaining poorly understood phenomena; the importance of imagination in the recreation of past events both historical and in the natural world; the interactions between developing knowledge and existing belief systems, and, not least, the importance of taking an international view on developments in knowledge.

Cuvier and his approaches to vertebrate palaeontology provided an important theme that ran through several presentations. The connections made by Cuvier between form and function in the fossils he studied and the environments in which they lived provided Martin with a link between his early work on brachiopods and his later historical writings. In parallel, Cuvier's analogies between the use of coins and inscriptions as time markers in human history and the similar use of fossils in geohistory formed a bridge between the methods of historians and geologists.

Imagination based on analogies was illustrated in a presentation that began with the early modern consideration of ammonites and their similarities of shape to curled rams' horns, and went on to discuss how the trade in pearly nautilus shells to Europe led to a new style of imagining based on analogies between a current species and fossils that could be related to it. Several similar modes of thought were also explored in a discussion of the attitudes to the fossil skeleton of the Megatherium when compared to a living Rhinoceros recently brought to Europe. While observation, myth and

folklore were all available for the latter, no such ready-made narrative was available for the newly discovered fossils.

Martin's recognition of the importance of visual methods as a way of imagining historical continuity broke new ground. Historians had not previously used tools such as Venn diagrams and flow charts to chronicle changes in ideas and attitudes. Even fictional narratives fell prey to some of his approaches as he showed that imagined 'scenes from deep time' actually form an historical continuum, which thus erased their 'otherness'.

Two presenters reviewed aspects of 'otherness' in the period when geology was a young science. The first looked at the perspectives of central European miners and those who commented on their tasks and risks, while the second examined developments along the fortified eastern frontier of Russia and the involvement of external expertise in exploring the region's economic geology. In both cases the interactions between somewhat isolated societies with primarily economic intents and those with expertise operating in a 'liminal' situation were identified as one of Martin's continuing themes.

Martin Rudwick at 90 Photo C Lewis

One of Martin's long-time collaborators, Hugh Torrens, gave a lively account of how the two of them were both engaged in recovering the papers of George Greenough, the founding president of the Geological Society.

Martin himself participated in the final session which drew together themes from the day. He modestly articulated his own distaste for creating founders or doyens in fields of knowledge and expressed his desire to eliminate such terms and their users. Despite this, others persisted, re-iterating his leading role in the emergence of a visual language applicable to history as well as his many other achievements.

Away from the lecture room we enjoyed lunch in what was once the ancient kitchen of the college and a closing reception held in Christopher Wren's magnificent library, where, as well as many rare geological books, we saw Martin's PhD thesis keeping company with Shakespeare folios, Newton's *Principia* and A.A. Milne's *Winnie the Pooh*.

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Unveiling Mary Anning's Statue

Lyme Regis, 21st May 2022

Phil James

Phil James gives us a personal account of a day that was very special for all historians of geology.

I found my first fossil, a flint *Micraster* echinoid, in our back garden when I was about 6 or 7 years old. I took it to school and despite not knowing what it was, my teacher was intrigued by the patterns. Along with her enthusiasm, it captured my imagination and fossils have remained a lifelong interest for the last 60 years.

Micraster echinoid from the James' back garden

In August 1968, when I was 13, my mother booked a holiday in Charmouth, right next door to Lyme Regis. A school pal had been the previous year, and places with names like Golden Cap had reached epic proportions in my mind. Dad and I found a beautiful large fossil nautilus under the cliffs there during that week.

Here I am, on the left, hammer in hand, with my mum and two brothers and Golden Cap in the distance

Our splendid nautilus find, Hemicenceras egregium, 30 cm.

Now, over 50 years later, I'm not really sure whether I became aware of Mary Anning during that holiday. What I can say is that I have certainly been well aware of her over many decades since. I have visited Lyme Regis numerous times, but, although I am a great fan of public statues, sculptures – and, of course, the history of geology – it never occurred to me that there should be a statue of Mary at Lyme.

I'm sure others must have thought of the idea, but the ultimate eureka moment came when the fossil-mad 10-year-old Evie Swire asked her mum – and not for the first time! – why there wasn't a statue to Mary. Her mum, Anya Pearson, got in touch with local councillor Cheryl Reynolds to ask the same question. She made the point that 'we are very good at immortalising men in this country, but when it comes to remembering and celebrating the remarkable things that women have done we are, sadly, really bad at it'. To cut a long story short, Lyme Regis Town Council subsequently gave the go ahead, and the 'Mary Anning Rocks' campaign was born. It quickly gained the support of Sir David Attenborough,

Professors Hugh Torrens and Alice Roberts, author Tracey Chevalier and Drs Dean Lomax and Anjana Khatwa, along with many others. 'Mary Anning Rocks' was launched on Facebook in 2018 and, thanks to the tireless efforts of Anya and a team of enthusiastic supporters, the crowdfunding campaign eventually reached its target of £150,000. Sculptor Denise Dutton was appointed to design and create the statue and the target date for Mary's unveiling was set for her 223rd birthday on 21st May 2022.

As a contributor to the appeal, I received a ticket for the unveiling and was really looking forward to the day. Then, much to my surprise, in early May, I, along with other fossil collectors, received an invitation from Dr Paul Davis, the Geology Curator at Lyme Regis Museum, to attend an exclusive exhibition preview of 'Mary Anning Comes Home & The Charmouth Crocodile', at 7pm on Friday 20th May. Also invited was my friend Alan Saxon who, back in December 2013, had found the 'Boxing Day Ichthyosaur', a rare specimen of *Ichthyosaurus breviceps* which is now on display in the Charmouth Heritage Center.

Alan's 'Boxing Day Ichthyosaur'

Alan and I agreed to meet at Seatown at 1pm that day for an afternoon of fossil collecting. We set off westwards along the beach towards Golden Cap just as I had done with my father nearly 54 years earlier. Our target was to find green ammonite nodules fallen from the cliffs above. Nodules have to be collected speculatively in most cases, but just sometimes parts of the creature are showing on the outside. Much preparation work is then needed back home.

Here's an example of one I found that day. Although it has been partially crushed it is nonetheless interesting. It is a rather uncommon and almost complete *Androgynoceras maculatum*.

Androgynoceras maculatum.

Alan was particularly lucky to find a pair of the rare *Productylioceras dawoei* which I subsequently prepared, – these

Unveiling Mary Anning's Statue

Phil James

would have been rare even in Mary Anning's day, as they are migrant ammonites.

Prodactylioceras davoei

When we got to the museum that evening, we found it was packed. I think everyone bravely dismissed the chance of catching Covid! The event had been planned to launch the Geology Gallery's new display of the unique Charmouth 'Croc' donated by Paul Turner and Lizzie Hingley, and also a temporary exhibition showcasing B.J.M. Donne's portrait of Mary Anning (on loan from the Geological Society) as well as an *Ichthyosaurus breviceps* that had been collected by Mary Anning (on loan from the Sedgwick Museum, Cambridge).

The Charmouth 'Croc'

The *Ichthyosaurus breviceps* found by Mary Anning

It was a great evening which included addresses by Hugh Torrens and Dean Lomax covering the fantastic contribution Mary made to the early science of palaeontology – an especially noteworthy achievement for any woman, let alone someone like Mary,

who had a very limited education and even more limited financial means.

I stayed with Alan overnight in Devon, and our timing in getting back to Lyme was rather misjudged, but we just made it! Amongst the massive crowd in the area around the statue we managed to secure a rather precarious position on the steep grassy bank to the left. Mary's statue is in a wonderful position on the eastern end of Gun Cliff walk at the junction with Long Entry path. Mary looks to the east across the bay in front of Black Ven towards Charmouth and Golden Cap beyond. She is right in the area where she collected fossils 200 years previously.

It was a fabulous afternoon with much excitement from the crowd. There were presentations by Anya with her daughter Evie, Hugh Torrens, Tracey Chevalier, Dean Lomax (all pictured) and others. Alice Roberts (pictured with me left) along with Evie, now 14, and her mum, unveiled the statue to much applause. Mary holds an *Eteoderocheras* ammonite in her left hand, has her collecting basket on her right arm, and her faithful dog Tray is at her feet. It is a really beautiful statue.

Later in the day, Alan and I sat down for a well-earned pint. I spotted Tom Sharpe walking by and asked him to join us. We had a jolly good chat about the day and Mary. He was just the man to meet following the recent publication of his brilliant book *The Fossil Woman*. Afterwards we all walked back to a much quieter Mary's statue where Alan took a great photo for the James family archive! (bottom row, 2nd from left).

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All photos © P.James

OUMNH's William Buckland Collection

One of the great research resources at Oxford University Museum of Natural History (OUMNH) is the specimen and archive collection of William Buckland (1784-1856), pioneering geologist and Dean of Westminster. Buckland wrote the first scientific account of a dinosaur, proved Kirkdale Cave in Yorkshire was a prehistoric hyena den, promoted glaciation theory in Britain, and established the use of fossilised faeces in reconstructing ecosystems.

Buckland entered Oxford's Corpus Christi College in 1801 and was appointed Reader in Mineralogy in 1813 and Reader in Geology in 1818. When he died, in 1856, a huge volume of papers and around 4000 specimens, were given to the University. These were transferred to OUMNH when it opened in 1860. Divided into three broad sections (correspondence, papers, and teaching illustrations), this collection reflects the passion for geology that permeated Buckland's life.

William Buckland (OUMNH)

The correspondence includes letters from many leading scientific figures of the time, including Henry De la Beche, Gideon Mantell and Mary Anning. As Buckland's work was often reported in the press, there are also letters asking his opinion on geological matters or offering some of the specimens that can still be found in OUMNH today.

The papers relating to Buckland's research and teaching cover a wide range of topics and include notes and correspondence relating to *Geology and Mineralogy*, his famous 1836 'Bridgewater Treatise' which summarised the state of geological knowledge at the time. The greatest part of the archive, however, comprises his original teaching illustrations, including small field sketches and topographical prints as well as detailed sections and anatomical drawings, some of which are several metres in length. There are drawings by professional artists such as George Scharf and Joseph Fisher, but also many illustrations by Buckland's wife, Mary (née Morland), who was herself a talented illustrator.

A Unique Opportunity

OUMNH has recently been offered a unique opportunity to acquire another extremely important collection of material related to William Buckland. Passed by descent to the current owners, this separate archive consists of just over 1,000 items of correspondence, geological notes, works of art and family papers. They relate to Buckland himself and also other family members, including his wife Mary and their eldest son, the naturalist and author Francis (Frank) Buckland.

This additional material fits beautifully with OUMNH's existing Buckland archive, providing missing pieces of the jigsaw. Most notably, there is a substantial amount of correspondence between Buckland, his father and uncle relating to his early life in Oxford and his efforts as a young lecturer to establish a new Readership in Geology.

The 'new' archive also includes over 300 letters from the 1820s-1840s when Buckland was at the height of his career. Many leading geologists and naturalists are represented including Richard Owen, Roderick Murchison and Adam Sedgwick. There is also a rare letter from Mary Anning announcing the discovery of a young plesiosaurus. In addition, working papers by Buckland cover a wide range of subjects including bogs, sandbanks, coral islands, landslips and much about animals and their fossil remains.

One of the greatest treasures in the archive is a notebook belonging to Mary before her marriage to Buckland which contains outstanding ink and watercolour drawings of specimens. It emphasizes what an exceptional illustrator and naturalist Mary was in her own right.

Mary Buckland's enlarged drawing of the 1839 Axmouth Landslip (OUMNH)

If OUMNH is unable to acquire this important archive, it may well be broken up. The letters and prints of high commercial value could be sold individually, seriously detracting from the collection's importance as a comprehensive body of material. It is also possible that it might be sold overseas and thus lost to the nation.

To prevent this, the museum has begun a major fundraising campaign to purchase, catalogue, conserve and digitise this collection. If successful, we will combine it, physically and digitally, with our existing, newly digitised Buckland archive, making these important resources easily accessible to both researchers and members of the public for the first time.

If you are interested in learning more or would like to donate to OUMNH's campaign, please contact Museum Director, Paul Smith: paul.smith@oum.ox.ac.uk

HOGG's Cabinet of Curiosities is a chimerical space combining the personal passion of the classic radio show 'Desert Island Discs' with the broadly educational intentions of the newer programme, 'The Museum of Curiosity'. Dave Williams' contribution to the Cabinet introduces us to two fascinating characters and a well-known geological map as he tells us about how and why he became a geologist and went on to develop an interest in old maps.

It is a very simple tale, of an impressionable young boy's first encounter with a geologist in the foyer of the National Museum of Wales, in about 1950.

Annual summer holidays were spent at my grandmother's flat in Barry, from where a short bus ride took us to the beach at Barry Island. It was there that I found my first fossil, looking for all the world like a chunk of a large ice cream cone. After much pestering, I persuaded Dad to take me to

the museum in Cardiff to find out exactly what this strange object was.

*The 'Museum' in Cardiff
Public Domain*

Arriving at the imposing building, we climbed the steps and entered a vast forbidding hall, where a lady at a desk told us that she would: "get someone to look at it" – and disappeared.

Eventually a very old man, or so he appeared to me, came through to the desk and spent about 20 minutes explaining to me that this was a fragment of a large coral. He went on to tell me all about Carboniferous fossils. He was very gentle and scholarly and, most importantly, he explained all this directly to ME, who knew my place as a mere short-trousered child. I was very impressed – perhaps all geologists were like this?

All brushed up – an impressionable Dave Williams aged about 10

Photo D. Williams

The elderly, gentle man was Dr. F. J. North, the geology curator – actually then only in his early 60s. He made a huge impression on me; was it that the Welsh did things very differently from the English, or were all geologists like this? Years later, when deciding on A-levels, I think that F. J. North was on my side in my battle to do Geology & Biology,

rejecting the lean diet of Physics & Maths to which all 'good scientists' should aspire. Three years later at University in Leeds, I realised that North was not typical of all geologists, but by then the die was cast. I was already an apprentice.

But what was it that really turned me on to the history of geology and old maps? I remember long chats with Roy Boud, the departmental cartographer at Leeds, who introduced me to Smith, Macculloch and Phillips; a welcome break from failing pressure vessels and my PhD.

A rather less 'brushed up' Dave Williams explains an OU rocks kit to an always well brushed Kenneth Baker, Minister for Education (a puzzled Professor Ian Gass looks on), 1997.

Photo D. Williams

But it was buying an old map from Eric Morten, the bookshop owner and publisher in Didsbury, Manchester, that really made it serious! Eric was a most engaging character, a real bookman. He kept a wide selection of books, which I enjoyed browsing in his old shop, where he had given my daughter a Saturday job. He had lots of science books, but little geology. When, one day, I asked him about this anomaly, he told me that it was because 'my daughter is studying geology, and always takes the best ones'. He then thought for a moment before adding: 'However, there is one I didn't let her take; it's a map. Want a look?'

An engaging bookseller: the late Eric Morten

Reproduced with permission

He then proceeded to lay out, across the floor of the small room, the top 4/5ths of William Smith's 1815 *A Delineation of the Strata of England and Wales, with part of Scotland*, begging other customers 'not to tread on it – please just leap over the corner.'

I was stunned. The map was in rather poor condition, but it was only actually missing a couple of bits of Cornwall and a bit of the Devon coast. I had just made an Open University TV programme on 'Mapping', which involved borrowing an original 1815 Smith map from the BGS & Smith's cross sections from the Geological Society – all to be couriered to and from the OU TV studios at Alexandra Palace. Only the Professor and Head of Department's signature was weighty

The Cabinet of Curiosities

enough to authorise these loans, so what a surprise to see the same map laid out here on the floor of my local bookshop just a week later! Needless to say, I snapped it up!

I was due for a term in Virginia Tech the next month, so I took it along to find that Rachael Laudan was in the Earth Sciences department there. She was stunned to see this map coming out of a Man. United bag as she'd studied Smith's work for her PhD in London. She sent it straight off to be photographed. (HOGG members may have heard of Dr Laudan as she seems still to provoke a tirade from Hugh T. whenever he gets to Smith – although she long ago developed a taste for food history rather than geology!)

Section of William Smith 1815 Map as bought from Eric Morten

Photo D. Williams

When, at the OU geology summer school in Durham, I next had my annual chat with Gilbert Larwood (a real enthusiast for old maps), I told him about the map. Straight away he said: 'Dave, you must take the bottom bit of mine back with you and get a good copy made.' No mention of any signature or letter about this loan; Gilbert was a real gentleman! HOGG's may have seen this 'Larwood' map, since Gilbert's son, Jonathan, has had a display case made for it and it has been doing the rounds of UK museums since the Smith bicentenary in 2015.

Dave Williams

Although my map was in rather poor condition, with the linen backing coming off and some fading and minor paper loss, after careful conservation, it should be good for another 100 years or so.

Alan Howell, then at the Geological Society, did a splendid job of remounting it and incorporating a copy of the missing strip taken from Gilbert's map.

William Smith map after restoration work by Alan Howell.

Photo D. Williams

Post Script – a pleasing symmetry

Many years later Tom Sharpe, who was then curator of geology at Cardiff, told me that the magnificent collection of Smith maps at the museum had been largely assembled by one F.J. North, OBE, DSc. Frederick North was a man well ahead of his time. He left school at 14, attending night school for an external London BSc, in which he achieved first class honours, before going on to make a study of brachiopods to earn his PhD. He rose from assistant to become

Frederick J. North, OBE, DSc

Photo courtesy NMW

curator of geology at the National Museum of Wales, where he worked for over forty years, publishing widely on early geologists, Welsh geology, applied geology and museum collections. An early paper of his on geological maps was: 'From the Geological map to the Geological Survey', *Transactions of the Cardiff Naturalists Society*, vol. LXV, pp 41-115, 1932.

Dave Williams
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A column where historians of geology tell us something about their experiences in the field. For this edition we are delighted that Professor Cynthia Burek has kindly agreed to undergo the *GeoHistories* inquisition.

Cynthia Burek, Professor of Geoconservation at the University of Chester and recipient of the Geologists' Association 2022 Halstead Medal – presented for outstanding merit deemed to further the objectives of the Association and to promote geology – has many strings to her bow. As well as teaching in the areas of conservation, science communication, soils, forensic biology, and women in science, she also serves on the Steering Group of the Geodiversity Action Plan, the Association of Welsh RIGS Executive, Cheshire RIGS, and NewRIGS. She previously served on the English Geodiversity Forum.

Leading an OU field trip near Staithes

Cynthia is perhaps best known to HOGG members for her work to champion the neglected achievements of women in geology. She has served on the HOGG committee and, with her long-time collaborator, Bettie Higgs of University College Cork, Ireland, organised two HOGG conferences focusing on the role of Women in Geology; one in 2005 and the other in 2019 to celebrate the centenary of female fellowships in the Geological Society. She also edited the accompanying Geol. Soc. Special Publications that sprang from these events. In addition, in 2006, she organised a HOGG conference held at the Black Country Museum in Dudley about the history of Geoconservation. This also resulted in a Geol. Soc. Special Publication (No. 300), which appeared in 2008. Previously, she had also co-edited the 2005 Special Publication 241 on the History of Palaeobotany.

Cynthia, how did you first become interested in the role of women in geology?

In 1998 I got involved in organising a conference about the role of science in secondary education, sponsored by a Socrates grant from the European Union. It was called the Penelope Project, after the goddess Penelope, and involved organisers from three countries: the UK, France, and Spain. The lead partner was in Tenerife. The conference was run in

2001 for teachers from all over Europe. It was this conference that really got me interested in women in geology. I wanted to run a workshop about the history of women in geology, and when I came back to the UK I discovered that the only woman I could find anything about was Mary Anning. Well, I thought, this is wrong – and that's what started the whole of my research into early female geologists.

You seem to work a lot with Bettie Higgs. How did you meet her?

Bettie's an igneous geologist and geophysicist, completely different to me, because I'm a soft rock geologist. Although my husband actually worked with her in the early 1970s, it was the Open University (OU) that brought Bettie and me together. We were both tutors for the OU, and were on the same summer schools together. She was very interested in women and why they were being left out of early geology and all this sort of stuff, which is what I was doing. We really hit it off, and we've collaborated on research into women in geology ever since. Bettie and I have written many articles together for the Irish geological journals and magazines, and I've written a lot myself in the UK -- perhaps 60 or 70 articles all together. A lot of them are in more local journals, because that's the nature of the history of geology.

Lecturing to a group in the Saltscape Project, Northwich, Cheshire and being interviewed for Channel 4 TV's Grand Designs programme

Do you have a favourite HOGG related book?

That's really difficult because I can't really come up with one. Maybe the one that I used most rather than my favourite is the *Making of The Geological Society of London*, edited by Cherry Lewis and Simon Knell (Special Publication 317) which was published in 2009. This included my paper, 'The first female Fellows and the status of women in the Geological

A HoG's Life

Society of London', and that inspired Bettie and me to organise the HOGG conference, 'A Centenary Celebration of the First Female Fellows of the Geological Society of London', in 2019, and to edit the accompanying Special Publication 506: *Celebrating 100 Years of Female Fellowship of the Geological Society: Discovering Forgotten Histories*. As part of the celebrations, we dressed up as historical female geologists and I commissioned a special cake. I travelled down to London from Cheshire on the train with it in an enormous box – absolutely terrified that somebody was going to sit on it! But all was well, and it was much enjoyed.

Cutting the cake at HOGG's celebration of 100 years of women FGSs

Which HoG related achievements are you most proud of?

One would have to be my books. I actually gave a copy of *The Role of Women in the History of Geology*, the publication I edited with Bettie Higgs in 2007 (Special Publication 281) to the women's library at LSE. It was the first book they'd had on women geologists. When I became a professor, I was asked to go back to my old school in the East End of

Cynthia Burek

London to give out the prizes and make a little speech. I presented them with a copy of the book as well, to try to encourage the girls to study geology.

Another source of pride is having stimulated some of my students to recognise the role of the history of women in geology. The last of my PhD students was inspired to embark on his PhD after attending a Geologists' Association talk I gave in North Wales about women in the history of geology in north Wales. We got talking afterwards, and he ended up working on his PhD with me, based on the work of Gertrude Ellis (1872 – 1960) on graptolites. I supervised him at the University of Chester, and he handed in his PhD during lockdown. He was only doing it part time, and it took him 10 years. But he did it! He actually works as a chief geotechnical engineer on the HS2 project in London. And now he's Dr Keith Nichols. (See also the article by Keith and Cynthia in this edition of *GeoHistories*, pp. 23-25.)

Which historical geologist from the past would you like to meet – and why?

Definitely Catherine Raisin (1855 – 1945), the geologist I dressed up as during the Centenary of Women Fellows celebration at the Geol. Soc. I don't think she was ever 'officially' a professor of geology at Bedford College in London, where she was based, but she was very pro women and often employed female teaching assistants, paying their wages herself. She inspired her students, especially Doris Reynolds (1899 – 1985), who worked on metasomatism and granitisation. Raisin herself carried out research on serpentinites on Anglesey and across the world, and also did field work for Thomas Bonney (1833 – 1923). A real heroine in a man's world!

Cynthia dressed as Catherine Raisin

Cynthia, thanks so much for talking about your fascinating and varied work and interests for GeoHistories. I only wish we had space to publish more of your stories

Divine intervention

Geologist and science writer Nina Morgan searches for the 'source'.

For the public at large the Malvern Hills are probably best known for their water. They are famous as the water source for medieval holy wells, eighteenth century spas, nineteenth century hydropathic 'cures' and, of course, bottled Malvern Water.

Fact or Fiction?

Geologists now recognise that the sources of the Malvern waters are springs located along the boundary faults and within the Precambrian outcrop itself. Hydrogeologists would always argue that the locating of water sources is down to careful geological mapping combined with knowledge of the local geology. But not everyone agrees.

In November 2017 ten of the twelve water companies in the UK told the science blogger Sally LePage, via Twitter, that they used the practice of water divining, or dowsing. Despite the lack of any scientific evidence for its effectiveness, belief in the value of water divining continues to thrive and there remain many adherents, even among scientists.

Although the British Society of Dowsers (www.britishdowsers.org), an organisation founded in 1933 to promote dowsing, offers a wide range of training in the art, hydrogeologists generally remain sceptical. As they point out, a water diviner can walk over an aquifer such as the Chalk and predict that water will be found at a certain location, but a hydrogeologist knows that a well drilled almost anywhere on the Chalk will encounter some water.

Nothing new

The debate about water divining is nothing new. Henry Bolingbroke Woodward (1832-1921), Keeper of the Geological Department of the British Museum (now British Museum of Natural History) from 1880 to 1901, one of the founders of the *Geological Magazine* (*Geol. Mag.*) and its sole editor between 1865 and 1918, published a *Geol. Mag.* letter of his own in the November 1872 issue under the title The Divining Rod in Somersetshire:

Sir, -- One would imagine that the Divining-rod or Dowsing fork had become a thing of the past -- that in these "enlightened" days no man could go about with a forked hazel-twig pressed to his ribs and believe it could indicate a coal-crop, a metalliferous deposit or a water supply. Yet there are some who still cling without question to the faith of their fathers, on the principle that as it was in the beginning it should be now ... the fact appears that on the Mendip Hills the Divining rod is still used.

Woodward's incredulity about the continued use of divining rods elicited a speedy response and confirmation of its use from the East Anglian-based curator, prolific author and science populariser and geologist, John Ellor Taylor.

Taylor had met with a similar response when he suggested that geological science -- in the form of the newly published

William Whitaker
Essex Naturalist (1927) Vol. 21 Plate 11

... A few days ago I was travelling in company with a gentleman to whom I had been introduced, who is a civil engineer and architect. He was telling me of some borings he had to conduct in Essex, in the London-clay, for water. I immediately referred him to Mr W. Whitaker's recently published memoir on the London Basin, in which is given such a copious list of well and other borings, thinking these might help him. I was replied to with a smile of self-satisfaction, and presently informed that when he wished to find water, he always used a forked hazel wand, which plainly and distinctly "turned in his hand" in the direction where water lay, and that he had never known this plan to fail!

John Ellor Taylor Public Domain

Therefore, Taylor concluded, tongue firmly in cheek:

My purpose in writing is to recommend the practice to the Geological Survey, so that a corps of hazel-wand explorers might be formed and drilled! It would be a novelty to have a "Professor of the Divining Rod" at Jermyn Street!

There may be more to Taylor's mischievous suggestion than meets the eye. As a young man Taylor had had to choose between a religious and a scientific career, and grew up to be a companionable man of liberal and humane sympathies. In his teaching he aimed to reconcile orthodox science with reverence for the divine principle in creation. So perhaps the only reasonable conclusion Taylor could accept about the effectiveness of water divining was 'God only knows!'

References: Sources for this vignette include: letters from H.B. Woodward and J.E. Taylor, and a review of *The Geology of the London Basin*, in *The Geological Magazine*, (1872); Steven Plunkett's ODNB entry for John Ellor Taylor; the obituaries of Henry Woodward & William Whitaker in *Geological Magazine* (1921) and *Nature* (1925) respectively; and an article about UK water companies and divining by Matthew Weaver in *The Guardian* 21 November 2017.

For further reading about the history of geology in the Malvern Hills see *Malvern Rocks: geology in a Victorian Health resort* by Tim Carter -- prepared as a guide for the HOGG field meeting he led in May 2022. It is available for download from: <https://tinyurl.com/55s5yuut>.

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Nina Morgan is a geologist and science writer based near Oxford. Her new book, *A story in Stone: The geology of the Oxford University Museum of Natural History Building* is available from the author and via www.gravestonegeology.uk.

Future HOGG Events

Thu 20th October 2022 (Online at lunchtime: 13.00-14.00) *Unlocking Lapworth's Archive* with Rachel Brown, Project Archivist at the Lapworth Museum of Geology, University of Birmingham

Tues 22nd November 2022 (Online at lunchtime: 13.00-14.30) **AGM** – followed by a talk to mark the bicentenary of the publication of the classic and influential book *Outlines of the geology of England & Wales* by Conybeare and Phillips, with Dr Leucha Veneer

Thu 16th February 2023 (Online at lunchtime: 13.00-14.00) *Arthur Young and the first geological maps of Norfolk and Suffolk* with Dr Peter Riches

Thu 16th March 2023 (Online at lunchtime: 13.00-14.00) *Capturing Extraction: Geology, Photography and Institutional History in the Godfrey Bingley Archives – an intimate relationship between geology and scenery* with Dr Rebecca Jarman, University of Leeds

Tuesday 15th -Friday 18th August 2023 HOGG Conference and Field Meeting in Dublin, Republic of Ireland: *Aspects of the history and progress of geology in Ireland* (working title) 1 day meeting + 3 days field, museum and archives visits, led by Dr Bettie Higgs and Dr Patrick Wyse Jackson

September 2023 (Online at lunchtime 13.00-14.00, date TBC) *Identifying and understanding former glacial lakes: a history* (working title) with Dr Laura Eddey

October 2023 (date TBC) *History of geological discovery in polar regions* (Joint HOGG/GCG meeting at British Antarctic Survey, Cambridge. 1 day meeting + 1 day archives visit.

November 2023 (date TBC) Online at lunchtime: 13.00-14.30 **AGM** – followed by a talk *The Sir Arthur Russell Collection of British minerals – a collection of collections* with Roy Starkey

HOGG Website

Our main website at <http://historyofgeologygroup.co.uk/> continues to be upgraded. This provides easy access to all aspects of HOGG including details concerning our activities & events, online registration, archived materials, and subscription renewal. We also have a presence at <https://www.geolsoc.org.uk/hogg> where you will find some useful resources.

Social Media

Follow history of geology snippets and selected items of interest to HOGG members through our Twitter feed. Our username is @HOGGGroup. Latest tweets are visible on <http://historyofgeologygroup.co.uk/>, and past tweets can be seen by clicking on the Twitter icon at the foot of that page. All our tweets also appear at <https://www.geolsoc.org.uk/hogg>

HOGG Bulletin

The HOGG Bulletin provides up-to-date news of current and forthcoming events of interest to historians of geology. It is sent out to HOGG members and associates approximately every six weeks via the HOGG Jisc email list. Please forward all news of events etc. for inclusion to the Bulletin Co-ordinator, Andrew Hopkins at bulletin.hogg@gmail.com

GeoHistories is issued in April and October.

Please send copy by the 10th of the month preceding publication to the editor: Peter Lincoln (hoggnewsletter@gmail.com).

Front Cover: The newly unveiled Mary Anning statue at Lyme Regis.

Image courtesy of Phil James

The geological map used as the backdrop to the *GeoHistories* title was published in 1875. It is a French map from the *Atlas Universel en 67 feuilles* by Brue´ and Levasseur (plate No.18.) and is unusual as the projections are centred on Paris and its antipode. The geology on the map is from Jules Marcou's 1861 *Carte Geologique de la Terre* – the second world geological map to be attempted (the first was by Ami Boué in 1843). The great blank areas are due to Marcou insisting he only publish geology that was known rather than based on conjecture. As such, it is an interesting view on the state of geological knowledge in the mid-nineteenth century.

Image courtesy of Duncan Hawley under CC BY-NC 4.0